

HBM4EU

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HORIZON2020 Programme
Contract No. 733032 HBM4EU

Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 3rd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals

Deliverable Report

D5.8

WP 5 – Translation of results into policy

Deadline: December 2020

Upload by Coordinator: 17 March 2021

Re-Upload: 16 August 2021

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marike Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	07/07/2021 05/02/2021
Grant Signatory	Antti Koivula	FIOH	29/01/2021

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
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Acknowledgements

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2 Glossary

ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
AUC	Area Under Curve
BADGE	Bisphenol A Diglycidyl Ether
BE	Biomonitoring Equivalent
BfR	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
BLV	Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office (Switzerland)
BMDL	Lower confidence limit of the Benchmark Dose Level
BPA	Bisphenol A
BPB	Bisphenol B
BPF	Bisphenol F
BPM	Bisphenol M
BPS	Bisphenol S
CMR	Carcinogenic, Mutagenic, or toxic for Reproduction
Danish EPA	Danish Environment Protection Agency
DNEL	Derived No Effect Level
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA CEF panel	EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FIOH	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
HBM-GV	Human Biomonitoring Guidance Value
HBM-RV	Human Biomonitoring Reference Value
HED	Human Equivalent Dose
HEDF	Human Equivalent Dose Factor
HIA	Health Impact Assessment
HLNUG	Hessian Agency for Nature Conservation, Environment and Geology
INERIS	French National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks
KEMI	Swedish Chemicals Agency
LC-MS/MS	Liquid Chromatography - Tandem Mass Spectrometry

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LOAEL	Lowest Adverse Effect Level
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
NTP	National Toxicology Program (US)
P50	50 th Percentile
P95	95 th Percentile
PBTK	Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic
PC	Polycarbonate
PCPs	Personal Care Products
PFASs	Perfluoroalkyl substances
QA/QC	Quality Assurance/Quality Control
RA	Risk assessment
RAC	Committee for Risk Assessment (ECHA)
RCR	Risk Characterisation Ratio
RPF	Relative potency factor
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction
SD	Standard Deviation
SVHC	Substance of Very High Concern
(t-)TDI	(temporary) Tolerable Daily Intake
TRV	Toxicity Reference Value
TWI	Tolerable weekly intake
US FDA	United States Food and Drug Administration
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

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3 Abstract

The aim of this work was to demonstrate how Human Biomonitoring (HBM) data can be included in risk assessment strategies. Risk assessment was performed for three compound groups on HBM4EU's first and second list of priority substances: bisphenols, PFAS and UV-filters. In addition, a case study was performed on cadmium, exploring a possible link between cadmium soil contamination and human exposure via dietary sources using HBM data. This was a follow-up work related to the risk assessment of cadmium published as part of Deliverable report D5.5.

For bisphenols, risk assessments were performed for BPA and BPS. Measured BPA levels did not result in risk in the general population when risks were estimated based on EFSA's t-TDI value. However, for BPS, health risks in the general population were identified when low-dose animal studies were used as a starting point. For BPA, a risk for workers was identified especially in industrial scenarios, when using an internal threshold value from a worst-case scenario. Specific challenges observed regarding risk assessment for bisphenols are discussed in the report. A clear need was identified for more HBM data on occupational bisphenols exposure across Europe, covering various professional activities and sectors. This need is particularly pressing for other bisphenols than BPA.

The PFAS risk assessment was a combined risk assessment of several PFASs, performed using three different approaches. These included the Relative Potency Factor (RPF) approach, the Hazard Index (HI) approach, and the sum value approach of the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA). Using all three approaches, health risks related to combined PFAS exposure were identified in the European population. However, all these approaches have limitations.

The UV-filters risk assessment focused on benzophenone-3. The results indicated potential risk for heavy users of benzophenone-3 containing products. It was noted that Human Biomonitoring data on benzophenones is still limited, and the identified data gaps call for up-to-date and European-wide biomonitoring activities.

The cadmium case study was set to characterise the exposure through existing HBM and environmental data, with an emphasis to assess what proportion of exposure is from contaminated soil through dietary sources. The analyses revealed an indication that at least in certain European areas, the local diet might be a significant contribution to cadmium exposure. However, due to uncertainties discussed in detail in the report, the observed associations should be taken with caution. Next, the observed positive associations will be verified. In addition, cadmium intake values will be calculated using PBPK modelling, which will allow an update of the existing RA presented in the Deliverable report D5.5 (Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals).

Overall, more HBM data are needed for the substances. This work is ongoing in HBM4EU, and the RAs presented here will be updated when new data become available.

These risk assessments have been performed within HBM4EU to determine how HBM data can contribute to the risk assessment of chemicals. The outcome of these risk assessments has no regulatory implications.

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4 Introduction

The objective of task 5.3 in HBM4EU is to perform risk assessments (RAs) and health impact assessments (HIAs) for HBM4EU priority compounds, in order to demonstrate how Human Biomonitoring (HBM) can be effectively used in chemical RA and HIA strategies. This also includes the use of available HBM guidance and reference values (HBM-GVs and HBM-RVs).

In the first year of the project, the current use of HBM in chemicals RA was evaluated. In addition, examples on the advanced use of HBM under different regulatory RA frameworks were collected on HBM4EU's 1st list of priority substances (Deliverable Report D5.1 Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: analysis of the current practice and 1st examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals). To build on this work, RAs and HIAs were then performed in task 5.3 for a set of compounds on the HBM4EU's 1st priority list of chemical groups (Deliverable Report D5.5 Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals). The work exemplified different approaches on how HBM data can be utilised in RA/HIA, also demonstrating benefits and challenges.

Here is presented task 5.3 work on another set of RAs for compounds included in the HBM4EU 1st priority list of chemical groups, including bisphenols (BPA and BPS) and PFAS mixtures. For cadmium, a case study on cadmium soil contamination and human exposure via dietary sources using HBM data is included. In addition, the first RA for the HBM4EU 2nd priority list of chemical groups is included, on UV-filters (benzophenone-3). The work on these four compounds/compound groups is summarised in this deliverable. In addition, the complete report for UV-filters is included as an annex. Manuscripts for publication in the scientific literature are under preparation concerning the RAs on bisphenols and PFAS mixtures, and the case study on cadmium. In this deliverable, also an overview of the work in progress in task 5.3 is presented, including RA and HIA work plans on further 2nd priority list compounds: acrylamide, aprotic solvents, arsenic, diisocyanates, lead, mercury, mycotoxins and pesticides. The reporting of those will be in the Deliverable report D5.11, which is due in 2021 but is dependent on data availability from the WP8 aligned studies.

It should be noted that the work presented here is not intended to have regulatory implications. It represents example RAs, illustrating how HBM can be used in RA. In most cases, the RAs presented here will be updated when new data generated within HBM4EU will be available.

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5 Summaries of the risk assessments performed

In this chapter, summaries of the performed RAs and their main conclusions are provided. For more detailed information on UV-filters, please refer to the complete RA report, included as an annex at the end of this deliverable. Manuscripts for publication in the scientific literature are under preparation regarding the RAs on bisphenols and PFAS mixtures, and the case study on cadmium.

5.1 Bisphenols risk assessment

The RA on bisphenols was carried out for bisphenols for which sufficient data were available, namely bisphenol A and S. Hazard characterisation and exposure assessment for these two bisphenols were addressed within Task 5.2 of HBM4EU, as part of the derivations of HBM guidance values (HBM-GV). Bisphenol F was also addressed in task 5.2, and available HBM data are presented in this report. However, no HBM-GV could be proposed, either for the general population or for the workers due to insufficient data. Therefore, no risk assessment could be performed for this substance at this moment.

HBM data have been gathered from the HBM4EU data repository made available by WP10 of HBM4EU and a literature search was additionally performed. These HBM data have then been compared to HBM-GVs derived by task 5.2 of HBM4EU to calculate Risk Characterisation Ratios (RCRs).

Regarding the general population and BPA, HBM-GV_{GenPop} for total BPA in urine of 230 µg/L for adults and 135 µg/L for children, are based on the t-TDI derived by EFSA, by applying the PBPK model by Karrer et al. 2018 assuming a 100% oral exposure scenario. An alternative approach considering different scenarios with relative contributions of oral and dermal routes of exposure was discussed within task 5.2 and concentrations of urinary total BPA for those mixed scenarios were calculated. Although this approach was not recommended within task 5.2 given the high uncertainties underlying the estimations of relative contribution of each route of exposure, the calculated values of urinary total BPA were also used in this risk assessment for indicative purpose. The calculated RCRs were all below 1, both for adults and for children, for every dataset available, indicating that the exposure to total BPA for the populations sampled is safe considering the HBM-GV based on the t-TDI from EFSA. Even, when using the alternative approach with mixed scenarios calculated RCRs are still far below 1 and risk related to BPA exposure can be ruled out.

Internal exposure to BPA for the occupational population, is thought to result primarily *via* dermal exposure. A concentration of rounded 12 µg/L for total BPA in urine was calculated as biological threshold value not to be exceeded in workers, when assuming a 100% dermal exposure at the workplace, as a worst-case scenario. Indeed, it is likely that part of the dermal contamination of BPA is not absorbed through the skin but rather enters the body via hand-to-mouth contact. Moreover, there is always a background exposure caused by food sources. Since this value of 12 µg/L for total BPA in urine for workers is below the recommended HBM-GV_{GenPop} and since some reported background levels of total BPA from non-occupational intake already exceed it, no HBM-GV workers could be recommended within task 5.2. However, this value was compared to the few HBM data available for BPA occupational exposure, for indicative purpose. Out of the five studies performed on workers, three of them reported mean concentrations inferior to this value of 12 µg/L. A Finnish study performed in industrial settings, when pure BPA was used but which showed low air levels of BPA, raises some concern, with median urinary total BPA concentrations 10 to 20 times

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higher than this internal threshold value, and highest values more than 100 times higher. The last study performed in French cashiers, reported P95 values exceeding the value of 12 µg/L, but the exceedance was also observed for controls, which means that significant proportion of urinary levels also in cashiers may reflect exposure from food sources rather than receipts only.

Regarding BPS, HBM-GVs for the general population and for workers have been derived based on points of departures from animal studies. Two scenarios, depending on the key study used to derive the values, were proposed within task 5.2, leading to HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 0.26 µg/L (scenario 1) or 1.03 µg/L (scenario 2) of total BPS in urine. HBM-GV_{worker} were of 0.75 µg/L (scenario 1) or 3.03 µg/L (scenario 2). RCRs were calculated thanks to HBM data available for total BPS in urine, under both scenarios. For the general population, RCRs calculated under scenario 1 were all above 1, suggesting that the risk for the health of the sampled population due to BPS exposure cannot be ruled out. Under scenario 2, results are more heterogeneous with a high HBM-GV_{GenPop}, and thus, lower RCRs. However, the risk associated with measured levels of exposure to BPS still cannot be ruled out for a majority of age groups (mainly children and teenagers) across the different cohorts.

Only one study was found, with regards to the exposure of workers (cashiers) to BPS, leading to RCR higher than 1 for both cashiers and occupational controls, under both scenarios.

Overall, we see a clear difference between risk assessment performed for BPA and BPS exposure, with very low RCR regarding exposure to BPA contrary to those obtained for BPS. However, this is due to the fact that the HBM-GVs recommended for BPS are based on endocrine disrupting health effects in animals at very low doses, contrary to the values calculated for BPA based on the t-TDI from EFSA in 2015. This t-TDI is currently under re-evaluation and if at the end a new TDI based on low doses effects is proposed, the outcome of our risk assessment would change, and risk may not be ruled out especially for sensitive population such as pregnant women and young children. On the other hand, levels of confidence associated to the HBM-GV_{GenPop} and HBM-GV_{worker} for BPS were considered as 'medium/low' within Task 5.2 of HBM4EU. According to the conclusions of other ongoing initiative, as well as new data, could strengthen or change the outcome of the risk assessment proposed in this document. However, risk assessments presented here, exemplify how biomonitoring data can be used in the risk assessment of bisphenols and also challenges and uncertainties related to its use in bisphenols case.

Regarding the occupational field, currently available HBM data indicate that the risk from occupational exposure to BPA and BPS should not be disregarded. Nevertheless, there is a clear need for HBM data and studies to be carried out for bisphenols, across Europe, and for various professional activities and sectors. Moreover, a better characterisation of exposure routes and better effects associations using internal doses as exposure metrics would be beneficial.

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5.2 Approaches to mixture risk assessment of PFASs in the European population based on human hazard and biomonitoring data

Perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) are a highly persistent, mobile, and bioaccumulative class of chemicals, of which emissions into the environment are expected to result in long-lasting contamination with high probability for causing adverse effects to human health and the environment; some of them already at current exposure levels. The aim of this study was to refine the mixture risk assessment of PFASs taking three approaches for comparison, the so-called Relative Potency Factor (RPF) approach, the Hazard Index (HI) approach, and the sum value approach of the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA). The latter was based on EFSA tolerable weekly intake (TWI) value for the sum of PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, and PFOS.

Exposure data for the European population was gathered for adults and children from Human Biomonitoring (HBM) studies presenting blood serum/plasma concentration samples retrieved after 2014, to obtain the most up-to-date reflection of exposure. The exposure assessment was done deterministically, using median exposure values for HBM cohorts. Furthermore, hazard data was gathered for immunotoxicity and developmental toxicity for use in the HI approach, internal RPFs for liver effects were derived for use in the RPF approach.

The HI approach illustrated that there could be a risk for children and adults in the European population resulting from exposure to PFASs mixtures. In this assessment, more than 4 PFASs were included, which is an advantage over the other two approaches. Furthermore, it is based on human data, thereby not involving issues relating interspecies differences. However, this approach shows uncertainty with regard to the hazard data underlying the hazard indices. Due to the positive correlation of PFASs in these studies, it is not possible to attribute the observed associations to a single PFAS. Furthermore, some hazard data were based on cord blood, and were expressed against exposure data based on blood serum data in older children. This comparison between different matrices introduces uncertainty. Moreover, combining these epidemiological points of departure in the HI approach may have resulted in double counting, and interpretation of the risk therefore should be done with caution.

The sum value methodology led to the conclusion that the risk of exposure to the sum of four PFASs is adequately controlled for the median exposure in one of the four regions of Europe for adults (East) and for all regions for children, whereas for adults a cumulative risk characterisation ratio >1 was observed for the South and North regions. The risk in children is probably underestimated due to the use of exposure levels in teenagers, who on average are known to be less exposed compared to small children. This approach relies on human data, therefore not involving issues regarding interspecies differences. However, only four substances were included in the assessment, whereas exposure to more than four PFASs is apparent in the HBM studies. Furthermore, this approach assumes equipotency of PFASs at the internal level, whereas the internal RPFs for liver toxicity indicate that the potency of PFOS and PFNA may be higher compared to that of PFOA and PFHxS.

The RPF method showed that the median exposures for the sum of those same four PFASs are above the TWI for all regions for adults, whereas for children the risk characterisation ratios remained <1 . Also, here, data for teenagers may have resulted in an underestimation of the risk for children as higher exposed groups (e.g. toddlers) have not been incorporated sufficiently in the exposure assessment. This assessment relies on experimental animal data

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and assumes that the potency ranking is similar for different end-points in one species and that this ranking is similar in rodents and other mammals. This introduces uncertainty regarding toxicodynamics and species concordance. However, as such, potency of the different substances is taken into account. Furthermore, for comparison to the sum approach, only four substances were included in the assessment. This approach may be extended with more RPFs thereby providing a possibility to include more than 4 PFASs in the assessment in future. Furthermore, the RPF values will be more robust when they are further validated for other effects, sex, species, and life-stages considered.

This mixture risk assessment illustrates that HBM provides a highly valuable contribution to the assessment of the cumulative risk resulting from exposures to PFASs. It is inherent to HBM to reflect the aggregated exposure from different exposure routes and exposure sources and therefore reflects exposure from all potential sources. It should be mentioned that this current work is a scientific exploration of how to use HBM in risk assessment. This exercise presents several approaches to perform mixture risk assessment for PFASs that are based on pragmatism, and each approach has its strengths, assumptions, uncertainties and flaws. All approaches indicate that PFAS exposure may cause adverse health effects in certain segments of the European population, thereby confirming the conclusion drawn in the recent EFSA scientific opinion that considered exposure modelling from food sources as input for the exposure assessment.

It needs to be stressed that the P50 was taken as a measure of representative exposure in the average population. For inclusion of the highly exposed part of the population, it would have been possible to include the P95 in our calculations to obtain a more conservative measure of exposure. Either way, in this deterministic approach one relies on the assumption that the pairwise correlation among PFAS exposures is 1. However, from HBM studies it is known that pairwise correlations among PFASs vary, and that positive correlations are strongly dependent on exposure source(s) (EFSA 2020). Therefore, one could perform mixture risk assessment at the individual level, using the raw exposure data to observe the exposure of the mixture of PFASs for each person separately. This results in a more precise estimate of mixture exposure, and consequently also in a more precise estimate of the cumulative risk. Another option would be to use the entire distribution of each PFAS in the cohort and to estimate the cumulative exposure using a probabilistic approach, also taking into account pairwise correlations within the cohort. In general, it may be more preferred to perform probabilistic exposure assessment, taking note of the spread in the data (EFSA 2012).

For future research, we recommend to focus on a more thorough overview of HBM data to illustrate exposure to the European population and to consider paired blood-urine and whole blood concentrations as markers of exposure. Additionally, we recommend to further validate PFASs relative potencies for other effects, sex, life-stages, and species, and in particular for critical effect such as immune effects, to gain more insight in mode(s) of action, adverse outcome pathways and species-specific toxicokinetics for evaluation of species concordance. To further refine the methodology, we suggest to consider probabilistic methods, and to explore the possibilities for incorporating individual data in (mixture) risk assessment.

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5.3 General population risk assessment of UV-filter benzophenone-3

Benzophenone-3 is a UV-filter that is widely applied in a variety of consumer products, such as sunscreens and other cosmetic products, and paints and coatings in lower amounts. The hazardous properties of benzophenone-3 raise consumer concern regarding repeated exposure.

Under the scope of the HBM4EU project, the current study incorporated Human Biomonitoring data in the chemical risk assessment of benzophenone-3 (**Annex**). To address the societal concern about benzophenone-3 exposure levels, this study aimed to assess the exposure levels to benzophenone-3 in the European population and to determine whether those exposure levels are safe in relation to the toxicological properties of benzophenone-3. Additionally, this report considered how Human Biomonitoring data can inform the risk assessment case of benzophenone-3, whether the necessary tools can be acquired, and if this information is useful for policymakers.

The available Human Biomonitoring data on benzophenone-3 was gathered through a systematic review. Exposure was assessed with a meta-analysis of the biomonitoring data. The hazardous properties of benzophenone-3 were identified, and the critical endpoint (i.e., the adverse health effect occurring at the lowest dose) was determined. A provisional Human Biomonitoring (HBM) guidance value was based on a point of departure, reflecting the critical endpoint identified in hazard characterisation. The point of departure was derived from the dose-response relationship in an animal experiment and is the dose associated with no attributable adverse effects (i.e., the no-observed-adverse-effect-level; NOAEL). The risk of benzophenone-3 was characterised by comparing the exposure levels to the derived provisional HBM guidance value. Exceedance of the guidance value implied potential risk associated with benzophenone-3 exposure.

Systematic review resulted in the identification of 203 unique articles. Screening and selection resulted in 17 articles with biomonitoring data on benzophenone-3 in European cohorts. Data from 3 studies could be included in the meta-analysis. These 3 studies included BP-3 concentrations measured in urine samples in cohorts from Denmark, Belgium, and Spain that were sampled between 2010 and 2013. Meta-analysis resulted in exposure estimates ranging from 0.60 to 4.40 µg/g creatinine for the average consumer, and 16.30 to 392.00 µg/g creatinine for the extensive consumer. The most sensitive endpoint for the hazardous properties of benzophenone-3 was maternal and developmental toxicity. The point of departure considered appropriate was a NOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw/day, based on urine-stained fur, effects on food consumption and body weight, and decreased net maternal body weight gain in the dams, and skeletal variations in the skull and cervical arch structures in the foetuses at 1000 mg/kg bw/day. The derived provisional Human Biomonitoring guidance value was 333 µg/g creatinine. The exposure estimates of the average consumer did not exceed the provisional guidance value. The exposure estimates of the extensive consumer did exceed the provisional guidance value.

This study aimed to provide an overview of the Human Biomonitoring studies on benzophenone-3 available in Europe. Potential risk of extensive exposure to benzophenone-3 was implied. Human Biomonitoring data facilitated the risk assessment case of benzophenone-3 with empirically derived exposure information. Because the exposure data was from before 2017, the risk assessment presented here underlines the need for the amendment of the cosmetics regulation in 2017. However, it does not provide insight in the

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effect of the amendment, in which the maximum allowed concentration in sunscreens was reduced. The information from Human Biomonitoring was limited by data availability. Sub-ideal reporting of data in the identified biomonitoring studies limited the possibilities for the meta-analysis of exposure. Asymmetric geographical coverage affected the European representativeness of the sample. Lack of substance-specific information created uncertainty in the interpretation of biomonitoring data. This study implicates the importance of open science principles and detailed reporting in Human Biomonitoring. The identified data gaps call for up-to-date European-wide biomonitoring activities. Future research needs to refine the risk assessment of benzophenone-3 further. This study emphasises the contribution of empirical exposure data by Human Biomonitoring and highlights the importance of the HBM4EU initiative.

5.4 Cadmium case study

The background for the present work was the observation that there has not been obvious decrease in soil Cd concentrations and human background intakes in Europe during recent years, in spite of improved regulations and guidelines; moreover, in local regions and farms even a slight increase has been observed, particularly in Sweden. In line with this, the main objective of this study was to estimate whether there is a link between high soil contamination with Cd and human exposure via dietary sources.

This objective follows up the RA performed for Cd and reported in Deliverable Report D5.5 (Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals). This RA focused on older population (> 50 years) and dietary intake limit values, which were derived based on limit values of proteinuria and urinary Cd levels. The HBM exposure data from elderly, which was used for the existing RA, were limited to two studies: French ENNS and Spanish BIOAMBIENT_ES. However, the use of a PBPK model allowed also for prediction of HBM limit values for younger age groups, and was based on the data from the DEMOCOPHES study (women 35-45 years). Based on the exceedance of the external limit values and HBM guidance values for the higher percentile of exposure, the existing RA showed consistently that a reduction of Cd exposure in the general population is needed. The present case study was therefore set to characterise the exposure through existing HBM and environmental data, with an emphasis to assess what proportion of exposure is from contaminated soil through dietary sources.

Human Biomonitoring data was obtained within the WP10, task 10.4. The basis for collection of the HBM data was the research protocol "Cadmium exposure among European residents and its geographical variability". The datasets eligible for the research protocol were identified using IPCHEM and additional literature search. Based on the strictly defined procedure for bilateral sharing of individual data (WP10), single measurement data of 29 data collections were obtained, representing 12 European countries. The respective datasets included biomarker concentrations (Cd concentrations in whole blood, spot urine, 24-h urine, or whole cord blood), general information on the subject (sex, age in years, smoking status, occupation) and geographical location in terms of NUTS codes. The actual time period the datasets covered was 2007–2018.

Geospatial data was collected from the available European databases (concentration of Cd in topsoil FOREGS and LUCAS geochemical databases; percentage of cropland; consumption of inorganic fertilizers; agricultural areas; total and land area; motorway and other road network density).

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In order to link environmental and HBM data, for each single HBM measurement value, a value was assigned from the respective spatial datasets, using NUTS code as a key identifier. The HBM and environmental data were then correlated using multiple regression modelling, confounding for sex, age and smoking status. In order to take into account the pathway from soil through crops (food) to human intake, percent of agricultural or cropland was also used in the models.

Due to heterogeneity of the study datasets, which were distributed across different number of NUTS geographical units and different spatial resolution, the data analysis was primarily performed separately for each dataset and then grouped together by the type of population group (adults, children, teenager, newborns, pregnant women) and type of biomarker (blood, urine, cord blood).

The associations between soil Cd levels and Cd HBM levels, performed on the highest available spatial resolution, were not consistent either across different datasets, population groups or different types of matrices.

There were positive associations observed for some groups in some areas, which indicates there might be a link between Cd in soil and exposure level through consumption of local food. In order to confirm these observations, the food consumption data and Cd content in selected food types is being collected from FAO/WHO database and will be included in the interpretation and data analysis in the next step. In some countries, such as Slovenia, extensive databases on Cd content in different types of food are already available (Kirinčič et al, 2019). Because the food related data is available only on the national level, data analyses will be possible only on the country-level aggregated data

However, re-evaluation of associations based on data 'harmonised' on the NUTS2 level of spatial resolution revealed consistent positive associations between soil and HBM levels for children and adolescents (Figures 5 and 6), particularly for Cd blood levels, but not for urine. This indicates that in these two population groups, the environmental Cd levels are better reflected through Cd in blood. This is consistent with the conclusions obtained in some other recent studies (Bernard, 2016; Vacchi-Suzzi et al., 2016; Stajniko et al., 2017).

Adjusting the regression models for percent of agricultural land and/or cropland influenced the associations between soil and HBM cadmium significantly in all groups except newborns. In adults, the regression coefficient decreased in case of blood Cd levels, while it increased in children (blood) and teenagers (blood and urine). Additionally, there was also evidence of importance for adjusting for road or motorway network density. The highest effect of roads and motorway density on the association was observed in adults in case of blood Cd levels and in newborns (only road density), and a significant increase of coefficient due to motorway density also in children in case of blood levels.

The lack of data on the consumption of phosphorous fertilizer did not allow for complete assessment on a larger geographical scale. In the population groups where the fertilizer consumption data were available (Czech, Swedish, Slovenian and Slovakian), the association between fertilizer consumption (normalised for the size of area) and HBM Cd levels was positive in adults from Slovenia (observed for urine and blood Cd levels) and in children from Slovenia and Sweden (observed for urine Cd levels). Among the birth cohorts, positive association between fertilizer consumption and cord blood was confirmed in the Slovakian dataset.

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Due to the inhomogeneity of the data, its coarse resolution and lack of some potentially more suitable explanatory variables, the observed associations should be taken with caution.

Nevertheless, based on the associations presented in this case study, there is an indication that at least in certain areas there might be a significant contribution to Cd exposure through local diet. This only partly answers the policy question whether there is a link between soil contamination with Cd and human exposure. Therefore, in the next step, we will verify the positive associations observed using the Cd content in selected food items relevant for Cd exposure and consumption patterns for these food items collected from the FAO/WHO database. Additionally, cadmium intake values will be calculated using PBPK modelling, which will allow an update of the existing RA presented in the D5.5.

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6 Discussion and conclusions

RA for chemicals can be reliably performed only when there are enough data available to support it. However, for many compounds, lack of data is reality. Therefore, modelling of exposure has become more and more important in regulatory RA, although it includes a lot of uncertainties. These uncertainties can be reduced using measurement data to support the modelling, but this often means external exposure monitoring data, i.e. air monitoring data or measured data on contaminant levels in the environment or food. Instead, HBM would provide more accurate data on the total internal exposure, covering all routes of exposure. In addition to exposure assessment, inclusion of HBM in RAs would be beneficial to help improve their overall reliability and to reduce the associated uncertainties.

Previously, examples on using HBM data in risk assessment were given in task 5.3 Deliverable Reports D5.1 and D5.5 (Deliverable Report D5.1 Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: analysis of the current practice and 1st examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals, Deliverable Report D5.5 Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals). Here, we have provided further examples of how HBM data can be used in RAs. It should be noted that the work presented here is not intended to have regulatory implications. The work represents example RAs, illustrating how HBM can be used in RA. In most cases, the RAs included here will be updated when new data generated within HBM4EU will be available.

For **bisphenols**, the risk assessment for worker populations exemplified a special challenge related to different exposure scenarios and route-to-route extrapolations. This was evident for BPA, for which different exposure routes may result in different amounts of its active metabolite, and it is not possible to measure the amount of the active metabolite itself but rather its detoxification product. Nevertheless, a potential risk for workers was identified, especially in industrial scenarios with exposure levels 10-20-fold higher than background exposures. Regarding BPS, there are not enough data on occupational exposure to perform RA. In addition, the other bisphenols remain even less studied, and a clear need was identified for more HBM data and studies to be carried out for occupational exposure to bisphenols across Europe, covering various professional activities and sectors. This need is particularly pressing for other bisphenols than BPA.

Regarding the bisphenols RAs for the general population, the conclusions of other ongoing initiatives and new data could strengthen or change the outcome of the risk assessment proposed in this document. In this study, high RCRs were obtained for BPS in contrary to clearly lower RCRs for BPA. This is due to the HBM-GVs recommended for BPS being based on endocrine disrupting health effects in animals at very low doses, contrary to the values calculated for BPA based on the t-TDI from EFSA in 2015. This t-TDI is currently under re-evaluation, and if a new TDI based on low doses effects is proposed, the outcome of this RA would change. In such case, risk may not be ruled out, especially for sensitive populations such as pregnant women and young children. On the other hand, levels of confidence associated to the HBM-GV_{GenPop} and HBM-GV_{worker} for BPS were considered as 'medium/low' within Task 5.2 of HBM4EU.

The **PFAS** risk assessment was a combined risk assessment of several PFASs, and provides three different approaches for a mixtures RA. These were the RPF approach, the HI approach, and the sum value approach of EFSA. All three approaches indicated adverse health risks related to combined PFAS exposure in at least certain subsets of the European

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population. Therefore, also the conclusion drawn in the recent EFSA scientific opinion (2020), which considered exposure modelling from food sources as input for the exposure assessment, was confirmed.

However, all three approaches used have their strengths and limitations:

- Particularly the **HI approach** may over-estimate risk. Due to the positive correlation of PFASs in these studies, it was not possible to attribute the observed associations to a single PFAS. In addition, combining epidemiological points of departure in the HI approach may have resulted in double counting. However, the use of P50 values instead of P95 exposure values, as well as a lack of Human Biomonitoring data for toddlers, may conversely have led to an underestimation of risk. On the other hand, this approach included more than four PFASs, which was an advantage over the other two approaches. The HI approach was also based on human data, thereby not involving issues relating to interspecies differences.
- Also, the **sum value approach** relied on human data, but only four substances were included in the assessment, whereas exposure to more than four PFASs is apparent in the HBM studies. Furthermore, this approach assumed equipotency of PFASs at the internal level, which might not be accurate.
- The **RPF approach** was based on animal data, from which the potencies of the different PFAS were derived. This may be highly relevant, as the derived internal RPFs for liver toxicity indicated that the potency of PFOS and PFNA may be higher compared to that of PFOA and PFHxS. However, the assessment relied on experimental animal data and assumed that the potency ranking is similar for different endpoints in one species and that this ranking is similar in rodents and other mammals, creating uncertainty. While here only four PFAS were included in the RPF approach, it could be extended by introducing more PFAS.

Overall, the work shows the highly valuable contribution that HBM can provide to the assessment of the cumulative risk resulting from exposures to PFASs.

The **UV-filters** RA focused on benzophenone-3, and gives a good example of an initial RA to screen for adverse health risks. The results indicated potential risk for heavy users of benzophenone-3 containing products. HBM data was considered to facilitate the RA of benzophenone-3 with empirically derived exposure information. However, it was noted that Human Biomonitoring data on benzophenones is still limited, and the identified data gaps call for up-to-date and European-wide biomonitoring activities. Also, sub-ideal reporting of data in biomonitoring studies were identified, highlighting the need for guidance in this area. When further and more recent HBM data become available, this RA can be updated. An update with HBM data following 2017 could also provide insight in the effect of the 2017 amendment of the cosmetics regulation, in which the maximum allowed benzophenone concentration in sunscreens was reduced.

The main objective of the **cadmium** case study was to estimate whether there is a link between high soil contamination with cadmium and human exposure via dietary sources. This objective followed up the RA performed for cadmium, reported in Deliverable Report D5.5. This earlier RA showed consistently that a reduction of Cd exposure in the general population is needed. The present case study was therefore set to characterise the exposure through existing HBM and environmental data, with an emphasis to assess what proportion of exposure is from contaminated soil through dietary sources. Due to the identified uncertainties, the observed associations should be taken with caution. However, the

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analyses revealed an indication that at least in certain European areas, the local diet might be a significant contribution to cadmium exposure. Next, the positive associations observed will be verified. In addition, cadmium intake values will be calculated using PBPK modelling, which will allow an update of the existing RA presented in D5.5. This case study demonstrates the potential that HBM data can have to increase the reliability of an existing RA. In addition, it highlights the importance of HBM data in not only RA, but also for the following risk management measures. If it is unknown where the relevant exposure originates from, efforts to decrease it will not be efficient. This applies particularly to the general population.

Overall, RAs based on HBM data include uncertainties. However, uncertainty is inherent to RA at least to some degree, and uncertainties related to the use of HBM are often smaller than those associated with exposure assessment based on only external exposure measurements and/or modelling. In addition, HBM can be applied in RA for more than just exposure assessment. In the best case, HBM data, external exposure assessment and modelling can support each other, increasing the quality of RA. This of course requires that the quality of the HBM data is high, and the risk assessor has expertise to interpret it. Work on generating guidance on the aspects to consider when using HBM data in RA is underway within task 5.3.

6.1 Results in the light of policy questions and recommendations for future research

6.1.1 Bisphenols

The risk assessment performed in this document aimed at addressing the following policy questions (questions 3, 4 and 6 of the scoping document on bisphenols):

Are bisphenols exposure levels of concern for health?

Is occupational exposure of cashiers a health concern?

Are health risks age and gender dependent?

We saw that risk can be ruled out for different age and gender populations when comparing the available HBM dataset related to BPA exposure with the HBM-GV_{GenPop} for urinary total BPA derived in task 5.2 of HBM4EU and based on the t-TDI for EFSA. Risk could not be ruled out for BPS, when comparing the HBM data available in the general population with the HBM-GV_{GenPop} recommended in task 5.2 of HBM4EU. There is not enough data however to establish a correlation between the risk and the age or gender of the population. The difference in risk assessment between BPA and BPS is due to the fact that the guidance value for BPS have been set based on endocrine disrupting health effects in animals at very low doses, contrary to the HBM-GV_{GenPop} for BPA based on the t-TDI from EFSA. In the end, the risk assessment depends on the effects on which are based the guidance values and a re-evaluation of those values could lead to change the conclusion of this risk assessment.

Available HBM data indicate that the risk from occupational exposure should not be disregarded, and that protective measures need to be taken regarding BPS exposure. However, to be able to conclude to a possible health concern for cashiers, more studies are needed. In fact, more studies are needed to be carried out for various occupational activities for all bisphenols. Moreover, since exposure to BPA results in mainly dermal absorption for cashiers, and as dermal absorption leads to higher concentration of free BPA in plasma, which is the active form, measuring free BPA levels post-shift at the end of the workweek

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might help performing a better risk assessment for this population. However, analytical capacities need to be deployed and available more widely.

Human Biomonitoring data, as well as toxicity and toxicokinetics data, are also needed to assess the risk for other BPA analogues.

6.1.2 PFAS

Based on the current PFAS work, two policy questions can be addressed (Q1 and Q13, as posed in the scoping document of PFASs):

How can mixture effects of environmental and human PFASs mixtures present to date be estimated?

What is the current exposure of the EU population to PFASs and do they exceed Guidance values (reference and HBM values), where available?

Here, mixture health risk assessment of PFASs was performed by using and comparing three approaches: the RPF approach, the HI approach, and the sum value approach. We conclude based on our mixture risk assessment, that the combined exposure to PFASs in certain segments of the European population is too high and may give rise to adverse human health effects, thereby confirming the conclusion drawn in the recent EFSA scientific opinion. These exercises are also based on pragmatism and have their underlying assumptions, uncertainties and flaws.

In the future, it is important to include exposure studies that will become available within HBM4EU and in the public literature, for a more solid image of exposure to European small children, as well as data for adults that could shed light on exposure in the Southern and Eastern regions of Europe. In addition, we highly recommend performing studies that observe paired blood-urine samples and whole blood samples, to have a better insight in exposure to short-chain PFASs and the ratio between PFASs in blood serum and plasma.

To facilitate HBGV derivation, more information regarding human toxicokinetics, such as human elimination half-lives for PFASs, would decrease uncertainty of profound interspecies differences in toxicokinetics. To refine mixture risk assessment, we recommend using a probabilistic approach rather than a deterministic approach if data allows for that. In risk assessment, it is preferable to include exposure and effect data at the individual level. This would resolve problems regarding difficulties in point of departure setting, imprecise estimation of cumulative exposure to multiple PFASs, and uncertainties regarding interspecies extrapolation. Furthermore, these data may be used to study relative potencies among PFASs the human level.

We recommend validating relative potencies of PFASs for other effects, sex, life-stages, and species, and in particular for critical effects such as immune effects. We advise, complementary to this, to investigate mode(s) of action and adverse outcome pathways for PFASs to overcome data gaps and to shed light on species concordance.

6.1.3 UV-filter benzophenone-3

The aim was to assess the exposure levels in the European population and to determine whether those exposure levels are safe in relation to the toxicological properties of benzophenone-3. Additionally, this report considered how Human Biomonitoring data can inform the risk assessment case of benzophenone-3, whether the necessary tools can be

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acquired, and if this information is useful for policymakers. By answering these questions, we respond to policy questions 2, 6, and 9 from the scoping document on UV-filters:

What are current levels of exposure of the EU population to benzophenone UV-filters?

How effective was the restriction of BP-3 in reducing exposures in the EU population?

How can HBM4EU results feed into regulatory decisions and risk assessments (ECHA and EFSA)?

Exposure was assessed with a meta-analysis of the biomonitoring data. Screening and selection resulted in 17 articles with biomonitoring data on benzophenone-3 in European cohorts. Data from 3 studies could be included in the meta-analysis. These 3 studies included BP-3 concentrations measured in urine samples in cohorts from Denmark, Belgium, and Spain that were sampled between 2010 and 2013. Meta-analysis resulted in exposure estimates ranging from 0.60 to 4.40 µg/g creatinine for the average consumer, and 16.30 to 392.00 µg/g creatinine for the extensive consumer. The most sensitive endpoint for the hazardous properties of benzophenone-3 was maternal and developmental toxicity. The derived provisional HBM guidance value was 333 µg/g creatinine. The exposure estimates of the average consumer did not exceed the provisional guidance value. The exposure estimates of the extensive consumer did exceed the provisional guidance value.

Because the exposure data was from before 2017, the risk assessment presented here underlines the need for the amendment of the cosmetics regulation in 2017. However, it does not provide insight in the effect of the amendment, in which the maximum allowed concentration in sunscreens was reduced.

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7 Upcoming work

One of the main conclusions of the work performed in task 5.3 during the first-year of the project was that while HBM is generally considered by regulatory risk assessors as a useful tool, it is mainly seen as a 3rd tier method for refinement of exposure assessment. In addition, the current guidance on the use of HBM in RA was considered generally either limited or completely missing, hindering the use of HBM. One of the proposals made in D 5.1 to better include HBM in human RA and HIA was to collect and create successful examples on the use of HBM, which could be used as a basis for developing a harmonised guidance on the use of HBM in RA and HIA. This is the aim of the work in task 5.3.

The work in progress under task 5.3 is related to three main topics: 1) Updating the first RAs presented in the Deliverable report D5.5 with new HBM exposure data from the HBM4EU aligned and occupational studies, 2) Giving more examples on HBM use in RAs and HIAs, by performing them for the 2nd priority list compound group substances using HBM data generated in the aligned studies, and 3) Based on our results, preparing a guidance document for risk assessors on how HBM could be increasingly included in regulatory risk assessment.

Here, an overview of the RA and HIA plans for the work in progress in task 5.3 is presented on the following 2nd priority list compounds: acrylamide, aprotic solvents, arsenic, diisocyanates, lead, mercury, mycotoxins and pesticides. The reporting of these will be in the Deliverable report D5.11 but is dependent on data availability. Delays are possible due to the covid-19 pandemic.

7.1 Summaries of risk assessment plans for the 2nd priority list compounds

For **acrylamide**, RA will be performed concerning the general population and dietary exposure. The RA aims to provide an interpretation of population level biomonitoring data in a health risk-based context, in order to identify if the current levels of acrylamide exposure could be a concern. The key endpoint to be considered will be carcinogenicity. Exposure assessment will be based on new HBM data, which is expected for both adults and children from the WP8 aligned studies. The studies will measure acrylamide urinary metabolites N-Acetyl-S-(2-carbamoyl-ethyl)cysteine (AAMA) and N-Acetyl-S-(2-carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl)cysteine (GAMA). The hazard assessment will be based on an EFSA acrylamide RA (2015), which was a full RA of acrylamide in food and identified a potential risk for cancer for consumers in all age groups. HBM data was not used for the RA. In the RA under task 5.3, the EFSA CONTAM Panel BMDL10 value derived for cancer will be used. To relate the external and internal exposures, the biomonitoring equivalent (BE) approach by Hays et al. will be used (Hays and Aylward 2009; Hays et al. 2008).

RA will be performed for the following **aprotic solvents**: N-ethyl pyrrolidone (NEP), N-methyl pyrrolidone (NMP), N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) and N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC). The RAs intend to answer the relevant policy-related research questions from the Scoping Document, if the available data allows it. The RAs will cover the general population, and the key endpoint under consideration will be reproductive toxicity. Hazard assessment will be based on the newly derived HBM-GVs from task 5.2. As no exposure data is included for aprotic solvents in the HBM4EU repository, a literature research will be conducted to search for published data sources. In addition, the following HBM datasets will be used: the German Environmental Survey (GerES) V (2014-2017) data on children and adolescents for

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pyrrolidones, and German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB) data on students within the time frame 1995-2020 for DMF, if the data collection and analysis is completed in time.

For **arsenic**, the key endpoint for which the RA will be performed is cancer of the lung, skin and urinary bladder. The focus will be on the general population and dietary exposure. The aim is to assess the extra cancer risk (and margin of exposure) at the measured exposure levels. For hazard assessment, ECHA dose response (2013) for the carcinogenicity of arsenic will be used. Also, BMDL-values derived by EFSA (2009) and JECFA (2011) for cancer risk levels will be considered. The BE approach will be used to correlate the internal and external exposure levels. Exposure assessment will be based on HBM data from published studies. Uncertainties related to the assessment will be considered taking into account uncertainties both in the dose-response and exposure assessment using the current biomonitoring approaches.

Regarding **diisocyanates**, the three major compounds on the European market will be considered: methylenediphenyl diisocyanate (MDI), toluene diisocyanate (TDI) and hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI). RAs concerning the occupational population will be made for these three substances. If estimates on the numbers of exposed workers are attained, also burden of disease calculations are envisaged. Hazard assessment will be based on the newly derived dose-response curves for bronchial hyperreactivity (BHR) by ECHA's Risk assessment committee (RAC). For the exposure assessment, literature data and data from the Finnish Institute of Occupational Health's biomonitoring database will be used. A PBPK model developed in WP12 will be used to convert the internal doses to external doses, after which excess risk of BHR corresponding the measured exposure levels will be calculated, by applying the dose-response estimated by RAC.

For **lead**, environmental burden of disease calculations concerning the general population will be performed instead of RA, as the adverse health effects of lead do not have a threshold. The risk assessment will focus on integrated sources of exposure for the general population. The key endpoints under consideration will be developmental neurotoxicity in children and possibly also cardiovascular effects in adults. As a first step, a case study will be performed with available, recent HBM data from Slovenia. A broader approach will be added, if recent data are available also from other European countries. For hazard assessment, existing toxicological reference values and BMDLs derived by EFSA (2010) will be used.

Regarding **mercury**, discussions related to the needs for a RA or environmental burden of disease calculations are currently underway. As a first step, a bibliography review of WP13 will be taken into account in order to identify the main epidemiological studies examining effects of exposure to mercury (including methylmercury and/or inorganic mercury). Exposure-response information from these studies for developmental and neurotoxicity outcomes and others such as cardiovascular diseases or reproductive effects, will be considered. Oral route will be the preferred route. With this information, a dose-response analysis will be conducted in order to estimate a point of departure (PoD) to update the existing RfD (EFSA, 2012). On the other hand, the uncertainties highlighted in the EFSA assessment will be addressed, especially the use of PBPK models (EFSA, 2012). If recent HBM data is available, an update of earlier environmental burden of disease calculations on developmental neurotoxicity, based on the DEMOCOPHES data (Bellanger et al. 2013), will be performed.

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Concerning **mycotoxins**, RA will be performed for deoxynivalenol (DON) and fumonisin B1 (FB1). The focus will be on the general population (mainly dietary exposure), but also the occupational population may be included, if relevant exposure data is available. The two main policy-related questions that the RAs will aim to reply to are “Is the risk associated to human exposure to these mycotoxins characterised?” and “Is it possible to set a HBM guidance value for mycotoxins?”. The RAs will be performed using published HBM data and new data from the WP8 aligned studies regarding DON. Estimation of the external exposure (Probable Daily Intake, PDI) will be made through reverse dosimetry. The risk characterisation will be based on comparing the estimated PDI with the available external health-based guidance values, most likely Total Daily Intake (TDI). For DON, an HBM-GV will be derived under task 5.2. Therefore, for DON, risk characterisation will also include the comparison of internal exposure with HBM-GV.

The target **pesticides** substances are pyrethroids, for which a combined RA is envisaged due to their similar toxicity profiles. In addition, also chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl organophosphates may be included. The RAs will cover the general population and mainly dietary exposure. For hazard assessment, existing individual TDIs and other health-based guidance values will be used. Exposure assessment will be based on a sample RA based on the quantitative data on pesticide exposure in a subset of the SPECIMEn study, included in the aligned studies in WP8. An approach to assess combined exposure to pyrethroids based on biomarker levels will be developed, first starting from individual risk assessments. The HBM4EU approach, including BE- and German HBM-Commission approaches (Apel et al., 2020), and available PBPK models will be used to convert TDIs as biomarker levels.

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9 Annex: General population risk assessment of UV-filter benzophenone-3

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9.1 Introduction

The HBM4EU project has selected chemicals for research activities under the project in prioritisation rounds based on health and regulatory interest. In the second prioritisation round, the benzophenone-type UV filters were selected (HBM4EU, 2019). Benzophenones are lipophilic phenols chemically synthesised for their UVA and UVB absorbing and dissipating properties. Twelve designated benzophenone derivatives (benzophenone 1-12) are commercially available. Most benzophenone derivatives are not well-researched, but benzophenone-3 (2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-benzophenone; BP-3) is extensively studied for regulatory purposes as well as for scientific interest. Of the commercially available benzophenones, BP-3 is the most widely applied UV-filter in consumer products (DEPA, 2015; Liao & Kannan, 2014). BP-3 enters the European market in volumes of 100-1000 tonnes per year (ECHA, 2020). The current European cosmetics regulation permits maximum concentrations of 6% BP-3 as an active ingredient in sunscreens and up to 0.5% in other cosmetic products to protect formulations (EC, 2020). BP-3 can also be added to paints and coatings as a UV-stabilizer, usually in concentrations between 0.1 and 1.0% (DEPA, 2015). Under the scope of the HBM4EU project, the current study focuses on BP-3, based on usage and data availability.

Because of the widespread use of BP-3 in a variety of products, humans likely face aggregated exposure, including exposure combined and accumulated from all sources and through different exposure routes (Calafat et al., 2008; DEPA, 2015). For such aggregated exposure, HBM can be especially relevant for performing a risk assessment. A large body of human evidence implies rapid absorption and systemic exposure after oral and dermal administration of BP-3 (Gonzalez et al., 2006; Hayden et al., 1997; Janjua et al., 2008; Janjua et al., 2004). After absorption, BP-3 is partially metabolised into metabolites. Suggested metabolites of BP-3 are BP-1, BP-2, BP-8, and 4-OH-BP, with BP-1 strongly indicated as the main metabolite of BP-3 (Wang & Kannan, 2013). In both animals and humans, BP-3 and its metabolites are primarily eliminated through urinary excretion in free and conjugated forms (Hayden et al., 1997; Janjua et al., 2004; Okereke et al., 1993; Sarveiya et al., 2004). Total deconjugated BP-3 concentration is commonly measured in urine as a non-invasive biomarker for internal exposure.

Information on systemic absorption of consumer products containing BP-3 raised concern about the hazardous properties of BP-3 (EWG, 2019). BP-3 is registered under the EU REACH Regulation (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of Chemicals) (EC No. 1907/2006). REACH requires companies to register their substances with information on hazardous properties and chemical safety reports. However, reports from the US Food and Drug Administration and the Danish Environmental Protection Agency, concluded that for many sunscreen ingredients, including BP-3, not enough safety information is available (DEPA, 2015; Matta et al., 2019). Therefore, concern remains about potential long-term effects from repeated exposure to BP-3 with regard to carcinogenicity and

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endocrine disruption (CoRap, 2014; EWG, 2019). Because of the latter, BP-3 is currently under substance evaluation for endocrine-disruptive properties (ECHA, 2020).

There is a lack of knowledge of the potential risk of adverse health effects resulting from BP-3 exposure within the European population. Although many countries have conducted HBM studies, incorporation of this information in chemical risk assessment is not common practice yet, as its value in risk assessment is largely unexplored. No risk assessment for exposure of the European population to BP-3 using HBM data has been performed to date. Previously, BP-3 safety evaluations performed by the Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS) implied no risk to consumer health. However, its exposure estimate was based on use patterns of sunscreen and other cosmetic products (SCCP, 2008). HBM data on exposure from all routes and sources may contribute a higher tier of exposure information to the exposure assessment.

To address the societal concern about BP-3 exposure levels, this study attempted to incorporate available HBM data in risk assessment to answer the first research question: *What are the exposure levels to benzophenone-3 in the European population, and are those exposure levels safe in relation to the toxicological properties of benzophenone-3?* As part of the HBM4EU project, this study ultimately aimed to inform policymakers by gaining an understanding of benzophenone exposure levels in relation to potential health risks for European citizens through HBM data. Subsequently, the compatibility of HBM in risk assessment and the relevance for policymaking was considered throughout the BP-3 risk assessment, to assess the additional research question: *How can Human Biomonitoring data inform the risk assessment case of benzophenone-3, can the necessary tools be acquired, and is this information useful for policymakers?*

9.2 Methods

In the current chemical risk assessment, first, the exposure was assessed. Next, the hazard identification and characterisation were performed, and lastly, the risk was characterised. The exposure assessment was based on a meta-analysis of the available BP-3 HBM data, the hazardous properties of BP-3 were identified, and the hazard was characterised with the derivation of a provisional HBM guidance value associated with no attributable adverse effects. The risk characterisation compared the exposure levels to the provisional HBM guidance value to estimate potential risk associated with BP-3 exposure. The risk assessment addressed the first research question. The interpretation of these results and related uncertainties, as well as the usability of HBM data during the assessment process, fed into answering the second research question.

9.2.1 Exposure assessment

To assess the BP-3 exposure levels in the European general population, a systematic review was performed to gather all available Human Biomonitoring studies. The systematic review methodology was based on the CRD guidance (Centre for Reviews and Dissemination) and the PRISMA protocol (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) (Liberati et al., 2009; Moher et al., 2015). The review process followed the phases of the PRISMA statement: identification, screening, eligibility assessment, inclusion (Liberati et al., 2009). Articles were qualitatively included for the composition of the BP-UV filter exposure database with European exposure data. Articles were quantitatively included for meta-analysis of BP-3 exposure in the European general population.

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9.2.1.1 Identification of records

Records were identified with the search engine Embase.com (Amsterdam: Elsevier), which covers records from the MEDLINE and EMBASE databases. The search encompassed records published before the 23rd of March 2020. Database searching was performed using a comprehensive search strategy based on the concepts “benzophenone-3” and “biomonitoring”. However, broader concepts such as “benzophenone-type UV filter” and “sampling” were included as well to ensure coverage of all relevant publications. The strategy was further structured by incorporating Emtree-terms, used for indexing articles in Embase.com, accompanied by relevant synonyms as title/abstract/keyword search terms (see *Appendix 1* for the final search strategy). Search filters were applied to restrict record identification to only Dutch- or English-language studies performed on humans, published after 01-01-2006, with available abstract. In addition to database searching, articles reported within the HBM4EU project were identified (HBM4EU, 2019). Selected studies were manually scanned for relevant references as well.

9.2.1.2 Screening and selection

The identified records and the further study selections were managed in EndNote X9. In the selection process, pre-set criteria were applied to two screening phases. The articles were first screened based on title and abstract and then based on full-text papers. If the title and abstract screening provided a clear reason to exclude, records were excluded immediately. All records deemed potentially eligible after the title and abstract screening were analysed based on the full-text papers.

In this stage of the review, studies measuring BP-3, separately or in combination with other BPs, in all matrices were considered. The search focused on European studies, as this is the scope of the HBM4EU project. The restriction on the year of publication was imposed because, in 2006, the SCCS (then SCCP) published a scientific opinion on BP-3, documenting the attempted safety evaluations as requested by the European Commission (SCCP, 2006). The SCCS opinion in 2006 concluded that data availability was insufficient for adequate safety evaluation. Updated safety evaluations published in the SCCS opinion in 2008 (SCCP, 2008), led to the amendment of the cosmetics regulation in 2017, further limiting the BP-3 concentration allowed in cosmetics from 10% to 6% (EC, 2020). To ensure analysis of periods of constant exposure to BP-3 before and after the regulatory amendment, only data after 2006 was included.

Based on the latter considerations, studies were included in the review when meeting all the inclusion criteria, some of which reflected by search filters. Inclusion criteria applied in the study screening were as follows:

- 1) Human Biomonitoring data on BP-3;
- 2) European study populations;
- 3) Dutch or English language studies (*search filter*);
- 4) publication in or after 2006 (*search filter*);
- 5) abstract available (*search filter*).

Sample storage temperatures may affect sample stability and thus affect BP-3 concentrations in the samples. Therefore, research indicates that urine samples not analysed on the same day as taken should be stored at a maximum temperature of 4°C (Vidal et al., 2007). As BP-3 undergoes extensive conjugation and BP-3 is excreted in urine in both free and conjugated form, samples should be deconjugated to allow measurement of total BP-3

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(free + conjugated) (Gonzalez et al., 2006). Based on these considerations, studies were excluded from the review when meeting one of the exclusion criteria. Exclusion criteria applied in the study screening were as follows:

- a) non-human studies (*search filter*);
- b) no biomonitoring data;
- c) not analysing BP-3;
- d) analysing experimental exposure to BP-3;
- e) non-European populations;
- f) data sampled before 2006;
- g) no full paper available;
- h) urine samples stored >4°C;
- i) urine samples not enzymatically deconjugated.

After study selection based on the criteria, the overlapping cohorts amongst multiple included articles were removed. In filtering out the overlapping cohorts, studies with larger sample size, more detailed data reporting, and analysis of multiple benzophenones, were prioritised.

9.2.1.3 Data extraction and database formation

Study characteristics and data were extracted from selected studies and managed in Excel. The Excel database included the following study characteristics: article citation, sampling period, sampling season, country of sampling, and cohort descriptions and demographics (sample size, age, sex, weight, height, BMI). When studies only reported individual participant characteristics, summary statistics were derived in Excel and included in the overall database. Sampling information was documented as benzophenone, matrix, sample type, analytical method, and LOD or LOQ. If relevant, the urine dilution correction method was included (see *Appendix 3* for technical background of dilution corrections). Descriptive statistics of biomarker concentrations were extracted for all benzophenones (% >LOD/LOQ, mean (SD), GM (GSD), minimum, maximum, percentiles with 95% CI). Data was occasionally converted to ensure concentrations were harmoniously expressed in µg/L or µg/g.

9.2.1.4 Quantitative inclusion for meta-analysis

For the quantitative inclusion of studies in the meta-analysis, concentrations of BP-3 and BP-1 measured in urine samples of the general population were selected. The general population was defined as the non-hospitalised and non-occupationally exposed population. BP-1 is considered the main metabolite of BP-3. Consequently, BP-1 eliminated in urine partly reflects initial BP-3 exposure. Therefore, the current study assesses exposure to BP-3 both by analysing urine levels of BP-3 and by BP-3 and BP-1 combined.

Risk of bias assessment of individual studies

Studies with data on urine samples from the general population were assessed on the risk of bias (RoB). In order to assess meta-bias across studies and to ensure overall confidence in the resulting exposure estimate, the RoB of individual studies must be taken into account.

For assessment of RoB in the individual studies, an adapted version of The Biomonitoring, Environmental Epidemiology, and Short-lived Chemicals (BEES-C) instrument was used (LaKind et al., 2014). The BEES-C instrument is developed specifically for qualitative evaluation of the quality of epidemiology studies that incorporate HBM data on short-lived

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chemicals. The tool is presented in tabular form and consists of the study design components to be assessed in rows and color-coded evaluative tiers in columns. For current review purposes, The BEES-C instrument by Lakind et al. (2014) was further adapted to assess studies only on aspects specifically relevant for the quality of biomonitoring data. In the current adapted version (see Table 17), the components “biological effect biomarker,” “temporality” and “data analysis” were removed, and the criteria for the components “study participants” and “reporting” were slightly altered to fit the focus on HBM better.

Table 17: RoB tool; BEES-C instrument adapted from LaKind et al. (2014), NA = not applicable; GC–HRMS = gas chromatography/high-resolution mass spectrometry; GC–MS = gas chromatography/mass spectrometry; GC–ECD = gas chromatography–electron capture detector; GC–FID = gas chromatography–flame ionisation detector; SG = specific gravity; ICC = intra-class correlation coefficient; P95 = 95th percentile.

Study assessment components	Tier 1	Tier 2	Tier 3
Biomarker selection and measurement			
Biological relevance of exposure biomarker	Biomarker in a specified matrix has an accurate and precise quantitative relationship with external exposure, internal dose, or target dose.	Evidence exists for a relationship between biomarker in a specified matrix and external exposure, internal dose, or target dose.	Biomarker in a specified matrix is a poor surrogate (low accuracy and precision) for exposure/dose.
Specificity	Biomarker is derived from exposure to one parent chemical.	Biomarker is specific for exposure to more than one parent compound and is related to the mode of action of the mixture.	Biomarker is derived from multiple parent chemicals with varying types of adverse endpoints.
Method sensitivity	Limits of detection are low enough to detect chemicals in a sufficient percentage of the samples to address the research question	NA	Frequency of detection too low to address the research hypothesis
Biomarker stability	Samples with a known history and documented stability data or those using real-time measurements.	Samples have known losses during storage, but the difference between low and high exposures can be qualitatively assessed.	Samples with either unknown storage history and/or no stability data for target analytes.
Sample contamination	Samples are contamination-free from time of collection to time of measurement (e.g., by use of certified analyte-free collection supplies and reference materials, and appropriate use of blanks both in the field and lab). Research includes documentation of the steps taken to provide the necessary	Incomplete documentation of quality control steps taken to avoid contamination.	There are known contamination issues and no documentation that the issues were addressed.

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Study assessment components	Tier 1	Tier 2	Tier 3
	assurance that the study data are reliable.		
Method requirements	Instrumentation that provides unambiguous identification and quantitation of the biomarker at the required sensitivity (e.g., GC–HRMS, GC-MS/MS, LC-MS/MS)	Instrumentation that allows for identification of the biomarker with a high degree of confidence and the required sensitivity (e.g., GC–MS, GC–ECD)	Instrumentation that only allows for possible quantification of the biomarker, but the method has known interferants (e.g., GC–FID, spectroscopy).
Matrix adjustment	Study provides results either in the main publication or as a supplement for creatinine-adjusted, osmolality-adjusted, SG-adjusted, or non-adjusted urine concentrations, and reasons are given for adjustment approach.	Study only provides results using one method (matrix-adjusted or not)	No established method for adjustment (e.g., adjustment for hair)
Exposure-related Study Design and Execution			
Exposure variability and misclassification	Sufficient number of samples. Error considered by calculating measures of accuracy (e.g., sensitivity and specificity) and reliability (e.g., ICC). If one sample is used, there is evidence that errors from a single measure are negligible	More than one sample collected, but without explicit evaluation of error.	Exposure based on a single sample without considering error.
General Epidemiological Study Design Considerations			
Study rationale	Studies designed specifically to evaluate a priori formulated hypothesis.	Studies using existing samples or data to evaluate a priori formulated hypothesis.	Data mining studies without a pre-specified hypothesis; multiple simultaneous hypothesis testing
Study participants	Population-based unbiased selection protocol; cohort is well described and is a good representation of the general population.	Population-based unbiased selection protocol; cohort is poorly described and/or is a representation of a sub-population.	Very low number of participants and/or methods of sample selection and/or cohort characteristics are not reported.
Reporting	Study clearly states its aims and allows the reader to evaluate the number of tested hypotheses; reporting of descriptive statistics is extensive with some measure of dispersion.	Study misses a measure of dispersion and/or some descriptive statistics hindering insight into the entire sample distribution.	Studies that selectively report data summaries and lack transparency in terms of methods or selection of presented results and/or reporting of descriptive statistics is sub-standard with no P95 and or mean/median

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In case considerable RoB was concluded, studies were excluded from the meta-analysis. Conclusions were guided by recommendations within the HBM4EU project. HBM4EU specifically emphasises the importance of pre-analytical quality control measures for biomonitoring studies (HBM4EU D7.3) and the importance of sample size and representativeness. Within HBM4EU, the prioritised analytical method for BP-3 is LC-MS/MS with a LOD/LOQ below 0.5 ng/ml (HBM4EU D9.5).

Data synthesis for meta-analysis

Meta-analysis possibilities were limited as data inventory indicated limited reporting of descriptive statistics in the studies, with no confidence intervals around the percentiles available. Consequently, it was required to set limitations on what data to include in the current meta-analysis.

HBM4EU prescribes a sample aim that covers the defined geographic regions of Europe (North, East, South, West) (see *Appendix 2*). HBM4EU recommends only aggregating datasets with a sample size $N > 120$ to ensure the reliability of summary statistics (HBM4EU D10.2). In dealing with heterogeneity, HBM4EU suggests analysis regardless of method differences, and consideration of sensitivity and robustness of results afterward (HBM4EU D10.5).

As the provisional HBM guidance value is only comparable to volume-corrected or creatinine-corrected urine samples (see Section 4.2.1), studies with other dilution corrections, including specific gravity correction, were excluded from the meta-analysis (see *Appendix 3* for technical background of dilution corrections). Decisions on data inclusion followed these HBM4EU recommendations and were discussed at the RIVM.

9.2.1.5 Statistical analysis and reporting

For the meta-analysis of exposure, the current assessment calculated summary statistics by aggregating the descriptive statistics reported by the individual studies included. The statistical analysis was guided by exemplary strategies of the EFSA CONTAM panel (European Food Safety Authority Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain) and RAC (ECHA Risk Assessment Committee), which also incorporated summarised statistics across different studies in their assessments.

In the EFSA CONTAM panel opinion on perfluorooctane sulfonic acid and perfluorooctanoic acid, the exposure assessment was based both on food consumption diaries and biomonitoring data (Knutsen et al., 2018). The CONTAM panel calculated the median and range of mean values and of P95 values across the food consumption surveys, and the median of median values from the HBM data. In the RAC 2017 opinion on phthalates, the exposure assessment was characterised by a typical case exposure scenario and a reasonable worst-case scenario, to assess the average consumer and the extensive consumer, respectively (RAC, 2017). The typical case exposure is described by the summarising the median values and the reasonable worst-case by summarising the P95 values across surveys.

Guided by these exemplary statistical strategies, the current assessment calculated summary statistics for typical case exposure and reasonable worst-case exposure. The typical case exposure is described by the median and range (min-max) of median values from the included studies and the reasonable worst-case by the median and range (min-max) of P95 values. Descriptive statistics that were below LOD or LOQ were replaced with the

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corresponding LOD or LOQ value, conforming with the statistical analysis of the CONTAM panel (Knutsen et al., 2018). All statistical analyses were performed in Excel.

9.2.2 Hazard identification and characterisation

The hazard identification of BP-3 was described based on the information available in the REACH registry, from public literature and in scientific opinions from governmental institutes. Due to time constraints, not all research covering all endpoints could be evaluated. The information in the most recent scientific opinion on BP-3, published by the SCCS in 2008, was emphasised as the current European cosmetics regulation of BP-3 was based on that opinion (SCCP, 2008). Currently, the SCCS is drafting an updated version of the 2008 opinion on BP-3. For logical policy timing reasons, it was thus decided to derive the provisional HBM guidance value in the hazard characterisation from the same PoD that the SCCS incorporated in the risk assessment published in the 2008 opinion.

9.2.2.1 Provisional HBM guidance value derivation with the urinary mass balance approach

For the derivation of the provisional HBM guidance value, the urinary mass balance approach was applied, as proposed by HBM4EU Task 5.2 (Apel et al., 2020; Angerer et al., 2011; Aylward et al., 2009). The urinary mass balance method can be applied to substances that are primarily eliminated through urinary excretion and for which regular repeated exposure is likely. For such substances, the approach assumes a balance between substance intake and substance excretion, reaching a steady-state in the urine matrix. Under this assumption, the urinary excretion rate is a constant fraction of the intake rate (Angerer et al., 2011). The urinary mass balance approach is visualised in the diagram below (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Approach to derive urinary HBM-GVs from an animal POD (adapted from Aylward et al., 2009 and Angerer et al., 2011), in individual cases further AFs might be necessary (Apel et al. 2020)

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Using this method, a critical dose from an experimental animal study (animal PoD) was transformed into a human biomarker concentration consistent with that dose based on the urinary mass balance assumption. The animal PoD was first extrapolated to a human equivalent (external) toxicity reference value (TRV) by applying assessment factors (AF) to account for extrapolation uncertainties (see *Equation 1*). Factors for allometric scaling and remaining differences (AF_A) were applied to account for differences in toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics between experimental animals and humans. An intraspecies factor (AF_H) was applied to consider toxicological sensitivity differences between humans due to differences in biology (age, sex, health status, etc.). Default AF values were determined following the consensus in the ECHA guidance chapter R.8 (European Chemicals Agency) (ECHA, 2012).

$$\text{Equation 1: } TRV = \frac{\text{Animal PoD}}{\text{Overall AF}}$$

Next, a provisional HBM guidance value for the general population was calculated from the TRV, using *Equation 2*, with parameters defined as follows:

- **Provisional HBM guidance value (GenPop):** the provisional Human Biomonitoring guidance value below which no adverse health effect should be expected in the general population, expressed as the substance concentration per unit of urine volume or creatinine (mg/L urine or mg/g creatinine)
- **TRV:** toxicity reference value, the external human value corresponding to the animal PoD (mg/kg bw/day)
- **F_{ue}:** substance-specific steady-state fraction of urinary excretion, the daily proportion of the intake dose excreted in urine.
- **Daily urine/creatinine excretion rate adjusted to BW:** typical 24-hour urine volume or creatinine excreted, adjusted to default human bodyweight (L/kg bw/day or g/kg bw/day)

$$\text{Equation 2: } \text{provisional HBM guidance value(GenPop)} = \frac{TRV * F_{ue} (\text{substance})}{\text{Daily urine/creatinine excretion rate adjusted to BW}}$$

As the REACH registry dossier of BP-1 was predominantly based on BP-3 read-across, and BP-1 is generally less well researched, no separate provisional HBM guidance value could be derived specifically for BP-1. Therefore, the provisional HBM guidance value for BP-3 exposure was used for interpretation of exposure estimates based on both BP-3 urine levels and urine levels of BP-3 and BP-1 combined. The latter approach assumes similar potency for both substances.

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9.2.3 Risk characterisation

The risk characterisation of BP-3 included the calculation of the Risk Characterisation Ratio (RCR) (van Leeuwen & Vermeire, 2007). This ratio was calculated by comparing the typical case (TC) exposure estimate and the reasonable worst-case (RWC) exposure estimate to the provisional HBM guidance value, as described in *Equation 3* and *Equation 4*:

$$\text{Equation 3: RCR (TC)} = \frac{\text{Range of median values}}{\text{provisional HBM guidance value}}$$

$$\text{Equation 4: RCR (RWC)} = \frac{\text{Range of P95 values}}{\text{provisional HBM guidance value}}$$

RCRs greater than 1 implicated that the population assessed is partly exposed above the derived guidance value and is thus potentially at risk of adverse effects from BP-3 exposure.

9.3 Results

9.3.1 Exposure assessment

9.3.1.1 Study selection for data extraction in exposure database

Results of the study selection process are visualised in the PRISMA flow diagram below (Figure 4). Database searching resulted in the identification of 205 records, and HBM4EU provided an additional 21 records. The identification of duplicates led to the removal of 25 records. Overlap mainly occurred for the articles identified within HBM4EU and due to the identification of conference abstracts. The remaining 203 unique articles were screened based on title and abstract. In this phase, 8 records were excluded for studying animal models, 2 for clearly not concerning HBM, 13 for clearly not analysing BP-3, 11 for studying experimental exposure, 84 for sampling non-European cohorts, 2 for sampling data before 2006, and 5 because no full paper was available. For 9 articles, the second reviewer was consulted for a second opinion, and a consensus was reached. For 78 articles, abstract screening provided no clear reasons for exclusion. These 78 studies were eligible for full-text screening. In the full-text screening phase, 2 records were further excluded for not reporting HBM data, 4 for not reporting data on BP-3, 33 for studying non-European populations, 16 for sampling data before 2006, and 2 for unfavorable sample storage temperatures. Because of cohort overlap, 5 studies were removed from the selection. Manual scanning of the references of the initial set of selected studies provided one extra reference: Joensen et al. (2017). This publication proved to be the original study of one of the already selected articles, which was subsequently removed for overlap. In total, 17 articles were included in the qualitative part of the review. Data from these 17 studies was manually extracted into the database. Table 18 presents the study characteristics of the 17 studies qualitatively included in the review.

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

Figure 4: PRISMA flow diagram by Liberati et al. (2009) visualising results of selection process and data synthesis decisions

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Table 18: Study characteristics of the 17 studies included in the qualitative part of the systematic review, NA = not applicable; UHPLC-MS/MS = ultra-high performing liquid chromatography/tandem mass spectrometry.

Study	Country	Sampling period	Cohort information	Matrices	Relevant analytes	Sample type	Dilution correction	Instrument
(Iribarne-Durán et al., 2020)	Spain	05/2015 - 04/2016	N= 57 healthy women recruited at University of Granada	Menstrual blood	BP-1, BP-3, BP-6, 4-OH-BP	Full menstrual cup	NA	UHPLC-MS/MS
(Frederiksen, Nielsen, et al., 2020)	Denmark	02/2017 - 04/2017	N= 100 young men recruited at national military enrollment screening	Urine	BP-3	Spot	Osmolality	Isotope dilution TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS
(Frederiksen, Krause, et al., 2020)	Denmark	2013	N= 313 young men recruited at national military enrollment screening	Urine, serum, seminal fluid	BP, BP-1, BP-2, BP-3, BP-7, 4-OH-BP, 4-MBP	Spot	Unadjusted, osmolality, NA	Isotope dilution TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS
(Vernet et al., 2019)	France	07/2012 - 07/2013	N= 16 pregnant women from the SEPAGES cohort	Urine	BP-3	Pregnancy pool	Unadjusted	Online-SPE HPLC-MS/MS
(Husøy et al., 2019)	Norway	09/2016 - 11/2017	N= 144 government and university employees from two counties	Urine	BP-3	24h	Specific gravity	Online-SPE UPLC-MS/MS
(Sakhi et al., 2018)	Norway	01/2012 - 05/2012	N= 104, mother-child pairs from two counties; 48 mothers and 56 children	Urine	BP-3	First morning	Specific gravity	Online-SPE UPLC-MS/MS
(Krause et al., 2018)	Denmark	09/2012 - 08/2014	N= 200 pregnant women at amniocentesis in two Copenhagen hospitals	Urine, serum, amniotic fluid	BP, BP-1, BP-2, BP-3, BP-7, 4-OH-BP, 4-MBP	Spot	Osmolality, NA	Isotope dilution TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS
(Joensen et al., 2017)	Denmark	2007 - 2009	N= 195 FLG mutation carriers and controls recruited at national military enrollment screening	Urine	BP, BP-1, BP-2, BP-3, BP-7, 4-OH-BP	Spot	Osmolality	Isotope dilution TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS
(Adoamnei et al., 2018)	Spain	10/2010 - 11/2011	N= 215 male university students from the Murcia Young Men's Study	Urine	BP-1, BP-2 BP-3, BP-8, 4-OH-BP	First morning	Unadjusted, creatinine	DLLME UHPLC-MS/MS

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Study	Country	Sampling period	Cohort information	Matrices	Relevant analytes	Sample type	Dilution correction	Instrument
(Krause et al., 2017)	Denmark	06/2013 - 07/2013 and 11/2013	N= 55 children from two kindergartens visited in summer and again in winter	Urine	BP, BP-1, BP-2, BP-3, BP-7, 4-OH-BP, 4-MBP	Spot, first morning	Unadjusted, osmolality	Isotope dilution TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS
(Frederiksen et al., 2017)	Denmark	11/2007	N= 129 children and adolescents from (high)schools in the Copenhagen area	Urine	BP, BP-1, BP-2, BP-3, BP-7, 4-OH-BP, 4-MBP	24h, first morning	Unadjusted	Isotope dilution TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS
(Artacho-Cordón et al., 2017)	Spain	05/2015 - 07/2015	N= 14 hospitalised adults undergoing trauma surgery	Urine, serum, adipose tissue	BP-3	Spot	Unadjusted	Isotope dilution TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS
(Moos et al., 2014)	Germany	2007-2011	N= 157, 59 mother-child pairs from the Duisberg cohort and 39 males	Urine	BP-1, BP-3, BP-8	Spot, first morning	Unadjusted, creatinine	Isotope dilution online LC/LC-MS/MS
(Koch et al., 2014)	Belgium	2012	N= 8, four husband and wife couples recruited in Flanders	Urine	BP-3	24h	Creatinine	Isotope dilution online LC/LC-MS/MS
(Frederiksen et al., 2014)	Denmark	2011 - 2012	N= 565 pregnant women from the Odense Child cohort	Urine	BP-3	Spot	Unadjusted	Isotope dilution TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS
(Dewalque et al., 2014)	Belgium	01/2013 - 04/2013	N= 261, recruited from the general population living in the Liege area	Urine	BP-3	Spot	Unadjusted, creatinine	UHPLC-ESI-MS/MS
(Frederiksen et al., 2013)	Denmark	09/2011 - 12/2011	N= 290, 145 mother-child pairs recruited from schools in a rural and urban area	Urine	BP-3	First morning	Unadjusted, creatinine	Isotope dilution TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS

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9.3.1.2 Quantitative inclusion for meta-analysis

The results of the quantitative selection process are further visualised in the PRISMA flow diagram in Figure 4. Out of the 17 studies that were included in the review, 16 studies reported urine data (Table 18). Data from Iribarne-Durán et al. (2020) was removed from further analysis, as the study only included menstrual blood samples.

RoB assessment with the BEES-C instrument

The 16 studies on urine samples were individually assessed with the adapted BEES-C instrument (Table 17). Several studies failed to properly report on storage time and sample stability or included only one type of sample per participant. Based on the RoB assessment, five studies were excluded from the quantitative data synthesis. Data from these studies was fully excluded from the meta-analysis for considerable RoB resulting from extremely small sample sizes (N= 8 - 16), poor documentation of sample contamination precautions, poor reporting of descriptive statistics, and/or poor method sensitivity (high LOD/LOQ and/or low portion of samples >LOD/LOQ). Table 19 shows the considerable RoB conclusions for the five excluded studies.

Joensen et al. (2017) reported exposure levels separately for both the filaggrin gene (FLG) mutation carriers and healthy controls (see Table 18). Carriers of the FLG loss-of-function mutation show diminished skin barrier function, and data from these samples was thus removed from the analysis as it does not represent the general population. There was no reason to exclude the data reported for the healthy controls in this stage of the data selection process.

Table 19: Studies removed from meta-analysis for considerable RoB concluded, with main conclusions from the BEES-C instrument that added to the removal decisions (LOQ: limit of quantification; LOD: limit of detection; P95: 95th percentile).

Study assessed on risk of bias	Considerable risk of bias concluded with reasons per category
Koch et al. (2014)	<i>Method sensitivity:</i> high LOQ (2.0 ng/ml). <i>Sample contamination:</i> no detailed information on precautions. <i>Study participants:</i> N=8. <i>Reporting:</i> only average (SD) and no P95 reported.
Moos et al. (2014)	<i>Method sensitivity:</i> high LOQ (2.0 ng/ml), 26% of samples >LOQ. <i>Reporting:</i> moderate reporting, no measure of dispersion.
Artacho-Cordón et al. (2017)	<i>Study participants:</i> N=14, hospitalised population (patients undergoing trauma surgery).
Krause et al. (2018)	<i>Study participants:</i> highly selected subgroup (pregnant women at amniocentesis due to either clinical indication or maternal request). <i>Reporting:</i> no P95 reported.
Vernet et al. (2019)	<i>Method sensitivity:</i> 45% of samples >LOQ. <i>Sample contamination:</i> no detailed information on precautions. <i>Study participants:</i> N=16.

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Data synthesis for meta-analysis

Three studies were removed from data synthesis for sample sizes were $N < 120$ (Frederiksen, Nielsen, et al., 2020; Krause et al., 2017; Sakhi et al., 2018). Two studies were removed from data synthesis for merely reporting samples unadjusted for urine dilution correction (Frederiksen et al., 2014; Frederiksen et al., 2017). Two studies were removed as they only reported osmolality-adjusted samples (Joensen et al., 2017; Frederiksen and Krause et al., 2020) and one that only reported specific gravity-adjusted samples (Husoy et al., 2019). No studies reported volume-corrected samples.

9.3.1.3 Exposure estimates

Meta-analysis of exposure was performed on the final quantitative inclusion of three studies, reporting creatinine-corrected urine concentrations (Adoamnei et al. 2018; Dewalque et al. 2014; Frederiksen et al. 2013). Table 20 presents the cohort characteristics and study-specific descriptive statistics of creatinine-corrected concentrations of BP-3 and BP-1. Frederiksen et al. (2013) reported BP-3 measurements in first morning urine samples of mother-child pairs in Denmark. Dewalque et al. (2014) reported BP-3 measurements in spot urine samples from the general population in Belgium. Adoamnei et al. (2018) reported BP-3 and BP-1 measurements in first morning urine samples of male students in Spain. Adoamnei et al. (2018) did not report maximum measured concentrations.

Table 20: Cohort characteristics and descriptive statistics reported by the final three studies included in the meta-analysis of exposure. All concentrations (P50, P75, P95, max) are creatinine-corrected and thus expressed as mg/g creatinine. (N: sample size, M: male; F: female; age range: minimum-maximum age in years; LOD: limit of detection; NA: not available)

Study	Country	Sampling period	N/sex	Age range	Sample	Chemical	LOD (% > LOD)	P50	P75	P95	Max
Frederiksen et al. (2013)	Denmark	09/2011 - 12/2011	143 M/F	6 - 11	Morning	BP-3	0.07 (97.0%)	2.00	6.30	33.00	408.00
			154 F	31 - 52	Morning	BP-3	0.07 (98.0%)	4.40	15.00	392.00	2139.00
Dewalque et al. (2014)	Belgium	01/2013 - 04/2013	123 M	2 - 75	Spot	BP-3	0.20 (82.1%)	0.60	2.00	28.80	414.20
			138 F	1 - 85	Spot	BP-3	0.20 (83.3%)	1.30	4.40	33.30	141.30
Adoamnei et al. (2018)	Spain	10/2010 - 11/2011	215 M	18 - 23	Morning	BP-3	0.20 (65.6%)	0.96	4.60	16.30	NA
						BP-1	0.10 (97.2%)	1.60	3.10	9.90	NA

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Table 21 shows the number of studies with corresponding study information per European region as defined by HBM4EU (*Appendix 2*). The North, West, and South regions are represented by one study, and no data could be included for the East region. While the North and West European regions are represented by samples in a wide age range and by both male and female subjects, the South region only includes young male participants.

Table 21: Studies included (final total of three studies) per European region as defined by HBM4EU with corresponding information on sample size, sex, and age range (minimum-maximum age in years).

European region	Studies	Samples	Sex	Age range
North	N = 1	N = 288	M/F	6 - 52
West	N = 1	N = 261	M/F	1 - 85
South	N = 1	N = 215	M	18 - 23
East	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 22 reports the summarised statistics based on median and 95th percentile values of the BP-3 concentrations in Frederiksen et al. (2013), Dewalque et al. (2014), and Adoamnei et al. (2018). The typical case BP-3 exposure (based on median values across the studies) ranged from 0.60 to 4.40 µg/g creatinine, with a median of 1.30 µg/g creatinine. The reasonable worst-case BP-3 exposure (based on P95 values across the studies) varied between 16.30 and 392.00 µg/g creatinine, with a median of 33.00 µg/g creatinine.

Table 22: Summarised exposure estimates resulting from meta-analysis of three included studies on BP-3 levels in creatinine corrected urine samples

Chemical	Studies	Typical case (median-based)			Reasonable worst case (P95 based)		
		Minimum	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Median	Maximum
BP-3	N = 3	0.60 µg/g	1.30 µg/g	4.40 µg/g	16.30 µg/g	33.00 µg/g	392.00 µg/g

9.3.2 Hazard identification and characterisation

The information under REACH categorises BP-3 as non-sensitising, non-irritant to eyes and skin, and suggests no acute adverse effects (ECHA, 2020). Both human epidemiological and animal experimental studies have associated BP-3 exposure to reproductive and developmental toxicity (French, 1992; Philippat et al., 2012; Tang et al., 2013). Within the CLP regulation (EC No. 1272/2008) (Classification, Labelling, and Packaging), BP-3 does not meet the criteria for reproductive toxicity classification (EC 2020). Systematic reviews highlight varying links between BP-3 exposure and estrogenic, androgenic, and antiandrogenic activity frequently reported in vivo and in vitro (Ghazipura et al., 2017; Kim & Choi, 2014). However, the clinical relevance of endocrine effects is not always clear, and uncertainty remains over when the observed endocrine effects should be interpreted as adverse. Therefore, in the updated opinion of the SCCS, currently in development, the endocrine-disrupting properties of BP-3 are further under review. The current SCCS opinion on the safety of BP-3 in cosmetics, identifies maternal and developmental toxicity as the most sensitive endpoints (SCCP, 2008).

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9.3.2.1 Animal PoD

Based on a prenatal developmental toxicity study in rats, the SCCS concluded a NOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw/day as the critical dose (SCCP, 2008). The SCCS used this NOAEL as the PoD in the safety assessment of BP-3, and this PoD was also used in the current risk assessment. The original experiment adhered to the OECD 414 Prenatal Developmental Toxicity guideline and complied with GLP conditions (see *Appendix 4* for detailed experimental design of the original study) (OECD, 2018). In the highest dose group (1000 mg BP-3/kg bw/day), both maternal, as well as fetal toxicity, was observed. The dams showed urine-stained fur, effects on food consumption and body weight, and decreased net maternal body weight gain compared to controls. Fetal examinations illustrated morphological effects. Skeletal variations were observed in skull and cervical arch structures. These effects were considered indicative of delayed ossification. No attributable adverse effects compared to controls were observed in the lower dose groups (40 and 200 mg BP-3/kg bw/day). Therefore, the SCCS concluded on a LOAEL of 1000 mg/kg bw/day for BP-3 for maternal as well as prenatal developmental toxicity with a NOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw/day as PoD (SCCP, 2008).

In a more recent study from Nakamura et al. (2015), there was a significant reduction of spermatocytes in male offspring after maternal BP-3 exposure at doses of 3000 ppm (207 mg/kg/d) and higher. From this study, a NOAEL of 67.9 mg/kg/d may be derived. Currently the SCCS is updating the opinion on BP-3, in which this new study will also be evaluated. Depending on the outcome, the PoD used in this risk assessment will be updated.

9.3.2.2 Assessment factors

In accordance with ECHA guidance R.8, AFs for allometric scaling, remaining interspecies differences, and intraspecies differences were applied (ECHA, 2012). The guidance additionally prescribes an AF for exposure duration extrapolation. This AF is generally applied to account for differences in exposure between the experimental toxicity study and real-life. The developmental toxicity study tested 14 days of exposure, which is categorised as sub-acute (see *Appendix 4* for detailed experimental design of the original study). In real-life, human populations are likely life-long exposed and better fit categorisation as chronic exposure. To account for this difference, another AF of 6 would have to be applied for extrapolation of sub-acute to chronic exposure duration. However, the dose-distance between the LOAEL and NOAEL was a factor 5. Therefore, it was decided to apply the lower duration extrapolation AF of 3.

An overall AF of 300 was constituted by the following default AFs:

- Allometric scaling (rat to human): 4
- Remaining interspecies differences: 2.5
- Intraspecies differences: 10
- Duration extrapolation: 3
- Overall AF: $4 * 2.5 * 10 * 3 = 300$

9.3.2.3 Remaining parameters

The F_{ue} was obtained from two human experimental exposure studies (Hayden et al., 1997; Sarveiya et al., 2004). Hayden et al. (1997) report a BP-3 output in urine of 1-2% of the initial dose, 10 hours after initial dermal application to nine healthy adult volunteers. Sarveiya et al.

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(2005) similarly report up to 1% BP-3 of the initial dose dermally applied to three female volunteers, measured in urine after 48 hours. It was decided to incorporate an F_{ue} of 0.01 (1%) as the more conservative value.

The HBM4EU default average daily creatinine excretion was incorporated in the derivation of the creatinine corrected provisional HBM guidance value. The HBM4EU default creatinine value is based on the calculation in Aylward et al. (2009) and amounts to an average creatinine excretion of 1.4 g/L per day for both sexes combined. Adjusted to the default bodyweight of 70kg, as defined by ECHA R.8 and followed by HBM4EU, this amounted to an average creatinine excretion rate of 0.02 mg/kg bw/day.

9.3.2.4 Calculation of the provisional HBM guidance value

Table 23 presents an overview of the information and parameters incorporated in the provisional HBM guidance value calculation.

Table 23: Overview of parameter values incorporated in the provisional HBM guidance value calculation, with sources

Parameter	Value	Source
Animal PoD	NOAEL = 200 mg/kg bw/day	SCCS opinion (2008) on OECD 414 study
Overall AF	AF = 300	ECHA R.8 guidance
F_{ue}	1% or 0.01	Hayden et al. (1997); Sarveiya et al. (2005)
24h creatinine	0.02 mg/kg bw/day	HBM4EU default from Aylward et al. (2009)

Application of the overall AF to the animal PoD in *Equation 1* provided the TRV:

$$TRV = \frac{200}{300} = 0.67 \text{ mg/kg bw/day}$$

Incorporating the TRV and remaining parameters (Table 23) in *Equation 2* provided the provisional HBM guidance value:

$$\text{provisional HBM guidance value (GenPop)} = \frac{0.67 * 0.01}{0.02} = 0.33 \text{ mg/g creatine} = 333 \text{ } \mu\text{g/g creatinine}$$

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9.3.3 Risk characterisation

Comparing the typical case (TC) exposure range (0.60 – 4.40 µg/g creatinine) and the reasonable worst-case (RWC) exposure range (16.30 – 392.00 µg/g creatinine) with the provisional value (333 µg/g creatinine) in *Equation 3* and *Equation 4*, provided the following RCRs:

$$RCR (TC) = \frac{0.60 - 4.40}{333} = 0.00 - 0.01 = RCR < 1$$

$$RCR (RWC) = \frac{16.30 - 392.00}{333} = 0.05 - 1.18 = RCR > 1$$

For typical case exposure, the RCR was below 1, so median HBM results did not exceed the provisional value. For reasonable worst-case exposure, the RCR exceeded 1. Table 24 repeats the information from Table 20, with the HBM values exceeding the provisional HBM guidance value in bold. The P95 value reported by Frederiksen et al. (2013) for Danish females exceeded the provisional HBM guidance value. The maximum values for female participants and children in Frederiksen et al. (2013), and for male participants in Dewalque et al. (2014), exceeded the provisional HBM guidance value.

Table 24: Cohort characteristics and descriptive statistics reported by the final three studies included in the meta-analysis of exposure. All concentrations (P50, P75, P95, max) are creatinine-corrected and thus expressed as mg/g creatinine. Concentrations > provisional HBM guidance value in bold. (N: sample size, M: male; F: female; age range: minimum-maximum age in years; LOD: limit of detection; NA: not available)

Study	Country	Sampling period	N/sex	Age range	Sample	Chemical	LOD (% > LOD)	P50	P75	P95	Max
Frederiksen et al. (2013)	Denmark	09/2011 - 12/2011	143 M/F	6 - 11	Morning	BP-3	0.07 (97.0%)	2.00	6.30	33.00	408.00
			154 F	31 - 52	Morning	BP-3	0.07 (98.0%)	4.40	15.00	392.00	2139.00
Dewalque et al. (2014)	Belgium	01/2013 - 04/2013	123 M	2 - 75	Spot	BP-3	0.20 (82.1%)	0.60	2.00	28.80	414.20
			138 F	1 - 85	Spot	BP-3	0.20 (83.3%)	1.30	4.40	33.30	141.30
Adoamnei et al. (2018)	Spain	10/2010 - 11/2011	215 M	18 - 23	Morning	BP-3	0.20 (65.6%)	0.96	4.60	16.30	NA
						BP-1	0.10 (97.2%)	1.60	3.10	9.90	NA

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9.4 Discussion

While the SCCS safety evaluation of BP-3 indicated no safety concern, consumer surveys still observe fearful attitudes towards regular use of chemical sunscreens (EWG, 2019; SCCP, 2008). Confusion exists amongst consumers due to both worrisome reports and urges for consistent sunscreen application (NAIF, n.a.). Aiming to add to existing information on BP-3 safety, the present study incorporated HBM data in the risk assessment case of BP-3. HBM data successfully facilitated the risk assessment case of BP-3 by contributing empirically measured exposure data. Three HBM studies provided reliable data for the meta-analysis of BP-3 exposure in Europe. No established HBM-GV existed for BP-3. The necessary tools for the provisional value derivation could be acquired from public literature. Comparing the exposure levels to the derived provisional value implied potential risk of BP-3 exposure to the extensive consumer. There was no reason for concern observed regarding potential risks of adverse effects due to BP-3 exposure for the average consumer. Potential risk was implied for consumers extensively exposed to BP-3. Data availability, substance-specific information, and sub-ideal reporting of data remain challenges for HBM in risk assessment.

9.4.1 Meta-analysis of BP-3 exposure

In the systematic review, the coverage of the database search strategy was likely comprehensive. Database searching identified virtually all publications previously identified within HBM4EU (HBM4EU, 2019). Moreover, database searching proved beneficial in gathering 10 (out of the 17) relevant European biomonitoring studies not yet identified within HBM4EU. Many studies were excluded for studying non-European populations (in total N = 117). Those studies largely covered cohorts from Asia and the US. While this underlines the global interest in HBM, it also accentuates the need for promotion of biomonitoring activities in Europe. The 17 European studies included, frequently reported subsamples of larger population cohorts. Full cohorts were often not easily accessible and not entirely published. For many studies, the BEES-C tool showed potential bias due to poor documentation of storage conditions and sample stability, or inclusion of only one type of sample per participant. As these limitations were common denominators and are acknowledged by HBM4EU, they were no direct reason to remove the particular studies from analysis. LaKind et al. additionally acknowledge that many studies will have aspects scoring one of the lower tiers and consider it unlikely that studies will score the highest tier on all aspects. However, it is acknowledged here that these aspects added to the RoB of the individual studies, and consequently influenced the results of the exposure analysis through potential meta-bias.

Selected studies with urine samples (N = 16) displayed much heterogeneity in sample types (spot, first morning, 24h), urine dilution adjustment methods (unadjusted, specific gravity, osmolality, creatinine) and populations characteristics (country, age, sex). Besides, reporting of descriptive statistics was sub-ideal in all individual studies included. Therefore, decisions had to be made on what datasets to aggregate in meta-analysis to end up with summary statistics of a sample representative for the European population and sufficiently homogeneous to allow comparison of datasets. This resulted in a substantial loss of data. Consequently, the exposure assessment based on a meta-analysis of HBM data was limited by data availability, and the sample aim described by HBM4EU was not met (*Appendix 2*). The geographical coverage of European regions was incomplete, and the sample size generally low. The three studies eligible for meta-analysis, provided creatinine-adjusted samples from Denmark, Belgium, and Spain, and represented the North, West, and South

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European regions, respectively. The meta-analysis included both male and female samples for all age groups as defined by HBM4EU (age range 1-85), but not for all European regions. The East European region was unrepresented, and the South European region was merely represented by male university students from Spain, likely not reflecting all exposure patterns in Southern Europe. While homogeneity in dilution adjustments was obtained, some heterogeneity in sample types remained as the meta-analysis summarised data from first morning and spot urine samples. Previous research on BP-3 sampling reported moderate to high intraclass correlations between different types of samples and implied reasonably robust representation of longer-term exposure (Dewalque et al., 2015; Koch et al., 2014; Lassen et al., 2013). Still, single sampling must be interpreted with caution as actual exposure may vary primarily based on intake rate and half-life elimination (Angerer et al., 2011).

Variation in BP-3 levels was significant, with the range of medians varying up to a seven-fold difference, and the range of P95s varying up to a 24-fold difference. In line with expectation on consumer exposure, exposure distributions in all studies showed left-skewed data, indicating that most of the population was relatively low exposed. This underlines the use of the 95th percentile to quantify the reasonable worst-case exposure, to also protect the more extensive consumer at the higher end (RAC 2017). Frederiksen et al. (2013) reported the highest exposure values in females from Denmark. Interestingly, participants were sampled in fall, during which no extensive sunscreen use is expected. The maximum level of exposure from Frederiksen et al. (2013), could be considered an outlier. When compared to the other reported statistics, the next highest reported maximum was up to a five-fold lower. No particular cohort characteristics seemed to explain this high value. The specific population tested consisted of healthy Danish mothers with no metabolic disturbances, recruited from both urban and rural areas. Frederiksen et al. (2013) concluded that high female values were not unexpected in light of more extensive exposure to personal care products in general. This is in line with previous research reporting higher BP-3 levels in females compared to males and mothers compared to children (Gao et al., 2015; Sakhi et al., 2018). Along this line of reasoning, exposure sources could explain the lower values for male students in Spain representing Southern Europe. Studies on BP-3 exposure sources report frequent occurrence and high concentrations of BP-3 in cosmetic products, such as sunscreens, skin lotions, foundations, and lip and eye make-up (DEPA, 2015; Ko et al., 2016; Liao & Kannan, 2014). Self-reported sunscreen use has been strongly associated with BP-3 concentrations in urine (Zamoiski et al., 2015). While sources other than sunscreen lotions and other cosmetics have been identified as well, based on content and frequency of use, these are estimated to contribute only 10% of the exposure to BP-3 (DEPA, 2015).

The current exposure assessment was unable to include urine levels of BP-1 due to low data availability. The specificity of BP-1 concentrations in urine as a biomarker for BP-3 exposure is not ideal as it may have originated from initial exposure to BP-1 itself. However, BP-1 occurs as a parent compound in much smaller amounts relative to BP-3 (DEPA, 2015). The currently measured BP-3 likely underestimated total exposure to BP-3 as the parent compound since it would have partly metabolised to BP-1. Assessing both urine levels of the parent compound BP-3 and its main metabolite BP-1 would have increased the precision of the exposure assessment (Koch et al., 2006).

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9.4.2 Provisional value derivation and risk assessment

The provisional value derivation was based on the NOAEL as PoD from the SCCS (SCCP, 2008). Uncertainty was introduced as the dose-distance between the NOAEL and LOAEL was large, and the NOAEL was based on both maternal toxicity as well as developmental toxicity. This uncertainty was reflected in the decisions concerning the application of AFs. Prenatal developmental toxicity is often subject to a critical window of exposure. In that case, the AF for exposure duration extrapolation is less relevant (ECHA, 2012). However, when generic maternal and developmental toxicity are observed at the same dose level, the fetal effects observed are presumably unspecific and secondary to the maternal effects (Giavini & Menegola, 2012; Paumgarten, 2010). Specifically, it is plausible that the observed fetal effects, delayed ossification, were induced by the reduced body weight gain of the dams. Therefore, the NOAEL may reflect the generic maternal toxicity, and so it was assumed that the window of critical exposure does not apply. Because no duration AF was incorporated in the SCCS safety evaluations, and that the dose-distance between the LOAEL and NOAEL was five-fold, application of AF=6 for extrapolation of sub-acute to chronic was considered too conservative and the AF= 3 was applied.

The provisional value derivation method included some assumptions. The PoD is derived from an oral study in rats, while the F_{ue} is based on dermal absorption in humans. Also the most important route of exposure to BP-3 in real life is likely to be dermal. As there is no reliable dermal toxicity study which lends itself for the derivation of a point of departure, nor an appropriate study that compares both routes, it is assumed that the absorption and metabolism are the same in both routes. As the dermal absorption is generally lower than via the oral route, this will probably result in a more conservative guidance value.

The urinary mass balance approach assumes a balance between substance intake and substance excretion and, accordingly, derives the provisional value by application of the F_{ue} as a steady-state metabolic conversion factor (Angerer et al., 2011). In reality, substance excretion may vary based on intake-rate and half-life elimination. Inconclusive half-life evidence from both animal and human studies suggests possible bioaccumulation, which creates uncertainty in the F_{ue} value. Rat studies show biphasic elimination with alpha half-life 0.88 – 1.3 hours and beta half-life 15.05 – 15.90 hours (Kadry et al., 1995; Okereke et al., 1994). Matta et al. (2019) report a long terminal half-life in humans with a mean range of 24-31 hours for BP-3. The detection of BP-3 in human breast milk and adipose tissue might suggest possible bioaccumulation of BP-3 in humans (Schlecht et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2015). More substance-specific toxicokinetic data is required to improve the reliability of the F_{ue} . Compared to several other chemical substances, the current F_{ue} seemed to be on the low side (Asimakopoulos et al., 2014). Asimakopoulos et al. (2014) incorporated a F_{ue} of 2%, based on Hayden et al. (1997), in the transformation of internal estimates to external intake estimates. As the current study transformed external intake estimates to internal exposure levels, a F_{ue} of 0.01 (1%) was considered the more conservative value. In case the F_{ue} was in reality higher, the current provisional value is slightly overestimating the risk ratio.

Generalising the provisional value to the general European population should be done with caution. The F_{ue} was obtained from small studies and is thus likely not representative of the general population (Angerer et al., 2011). As toxicokinetic variations exist among age and sex groups, the F_{ue} represents only the fractions for a specific population. Daily creatinine excretion rates are also subject to interindividual toxicokinetics variations. The default value from Aylward et al. (2009) represents a predominantly male group of participants with an

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acceptable default bodyweight of 70kg assumed. Incorporation of this default value in the provisional HBM guidance value derivation likely affected the generalisability of the provisional value for the general population. Improved default creatinine excretion values are considered within HBM4EU WP5. While interindividual variation in the F_{ue} and typical creatinine values might affect the representativeness, these variations were partly accounted for by application of the assessment factors. Besides, these uncertainties are urine matrix specific and do not make HBM data unusable. More extensive knowledge on the F_{ue} and average creatinine excretion values in different population groups might lower the intraspecies AF and further refine the risk assessment.

The risk assessment of BP-3 presented here should be interpreted as preliminary. It is illustrative of the challenges faced when incorporating HBM data. Potential risk was implied for consumers extensively exposed to BP-3. Since exposure estimates were derived from HBM data sampled between 2010 and 2013, and the cosmetics regulation has been amended in 2017, the current assessment underlines the amendment. However, it does not provide extra insight into consumer safety and risk management for the present situation specifically. As the amended regulation permits lower amounts of BP-3 in sunscreens and BP-3 is seemingly being replaced with other UV-filters, the present risk may be reduced (DEPA, 2015). However, further refined risk assessment of BP-3 is required to evaluate the safety of the present use of BP-3 adequately.

9.4.3 Implications for future research

The risk assessment of BP-3 could be further refined by more substance-specific toxicokinetic research. Further toxicokinetic evidence on BP-3 metabolism and elimination might improve the reliability of the F_{ue} and allow for more precise consideration of metabolites. Incorporation of HBM data on BP-3 metabolites could improve the precision of the BP-3 exposure assessment. Up-to-date HBM data is needed to assess the safety of the present use of BP-3 and inform current policies. More detailed research on exposure sources of BP-3 would benefit the relevance of HBM data in risk management. While chemicals like BP-3 are sometimes added to consumer products for health-benefiting reasons, such as UV protection, this study indicates the public health importance of assessing the chemical body burden when considering the safety and health benefit of such products.

The challenges in this assessment indicated some general improvements to benefit further incorporation of HBM research. The identified data gaps ask for up-to-date European-wide biomonitoring activities. HBM data from larger population cohorts needs to be more easily accessible, which calls for Open Science principles. Data comparability ideally asks for harmonised datasets. More detailed reporting of statistics for total samples analysed, and stratified per age and sex group, would substantially improve the possibilities of aggregating data. Reliable sampling is of utmost importance in all applications of HBM. Therefore, this report emphasises the HBM4EU recommendations on laboratory conditions and documentation. Repeated sampling or exposure questionnaires would aid the interpretation of exposure assessment and improve the comparability of data with reference values in risk assessment.

More HBM data can be beneficial in further analysis. Subgroup analysis of HBM data might provide useful insights to chemical policymaking aimed at highly exposed and vulnerable groups. Time-trend analysis based on HBM can quantify the actual population-wide effects of specific policy changes. In the context of the animal testing ban, HBM can potentially aid in

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providing more human-specific information. Besides facilitating risk assessment, HBM data is valuable in confirming alternatively derived exposure information.

9.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this preliminary risk assessment of BP-3 implied potential risk to extensive consumers and underlines the amendment of the cosmetics regulation in 2017. HBM successfully facilitated the current risk assessment, but further refined safety evaluation of BP-3 is required to address consumer concern adequately. This report urges HBM studies to adhere to HBM4EU recommendations as these will likely add to the relevance and usefulness of HBM for chemical policymaking in the future. This study notes the value of empirical HBM data and highlights the importance of the HBM4EU initiative in advancing and coordinating biomonitoring research in Europe.

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9.7 Appendix 1: Database search strategy

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Embase®

Embase Session Results		RELX™
No.	Query	Results
#13	(#9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12) AND ([dutch]/lim OR [english]/lim) AND [humans]/lim AND [abstracts]/lim AND [2006-2020]/py	205
#12	#4 AND #8	243
#11	#4 AND #7	16
#10	#4 AND #6	103
#9	#4 AND #5	96
#8	'urine sample':ti,ab,kw OR 'urinary sample':ti,ab,kw OR 'urine concentration':ti,ab,kw OR 'urinary concentration':ti,ab,kw OR 'urine level':ti,ab,kw OR 'urinary level':ti,ab,kw OR 'blood sample':ti,ab,kw OR 'blood concentration':ti,ab,kw OR 'blood level':ti,ab,kw OR 'plasma sample':ti,ab,kw OR 'plasma concentration':ti,ab,kw OR 'plasma level':ti,ab,kw OR 'serum sample':ti,ab,kw OR 'serum concentration':ti,ab,kw OR 'serum level':ti,ab,kw OR 'amniotic fluid sample':ti,ab,kw OR 'amniotic fluid concentration':ti,ab,kw OR 'amniotic fluid level':ti,ab,kw OR 'tissue sample':ti,ab,kw OR 'tissue concentration':ti,ab,kw OR 'tissue level':ti,ab,kw	826,200
#7	'sampling'/exp/mj	27,435
#6	'analytical parameters'/exp/mj	511,369
#5	'biological marker'/exp OR 'biological monitoring'/exp OR 'biological monitoring':ti,ab,kw OR 'biomonitoring':ti,ab,kw	315,593
#4	#1 OR #2 OR #3	6,499
#3	'benzophenone'/exp OR benzophenone':ti,ab,kw OR 'benzophenone derivative'/exp OR 'benzophenone derivative':ti,ab,kw OR 'benzophenone-type uv filter':ti,ab,kw	6,003
#2	'2 hydroxy 4 methoxybenzophenone':ti,ab,kw OR 'advastab 45':ti,ab,kw OR 'anuvex':ti,ab,kw OR 'benzophenone 3':ti,ab,kw OR 'benzophenone-3':ti,ab,kw OR 'chimassorb 90':ti,ab,kw OR 'cyasorb uv 9':ti,ab,kw OR 'eusolex 4360':ti,ab,kw OR 'lankromark le29':ti,ab,kw OR 'neo heliopan bb':ti,ab,kw OR 'nsc 7778':ti,ab,kw OR 'ongrostab hmb':ti,ab,kw OR 'rhodialux a':ti,ab,kw OR 'ritaphenone 3':ti,ab,kw	689
#1	'oxybenzone'/exp OR 'oxybenzone':ti,ab,kw	1,391

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9.8 Appendix 2: HBM4EU representative EU sample aim

HBM4EU WP7 provides guidelines in striving for a study sample representative of the European population. The ideal sample aim, as described by HBM4EU, includes N=150 males and N=150 females per age group (0-2y, 3-5y, 6-11y, 12-19y, 20-39y, 40-59y, 60-79y) per country. For reasons of feasibility, HBM4EU reduced this ideal to the more practical aim of 3 countries per European region (North, East, South, West). HBM4EU divides the European regions as follows:

- *North*: Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden, United Kingdom
- *West*: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Switzerland
- *South*: Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain
- *East*: Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia
- *Other*: Israel

9.9 Appendix 3: Technical background urine samples and dilution adjustments

Urine sampling can be a non-invasive method to gather HBM data. Urine sample types are spot samples, first morning samples, or 24h samples. To account for differences in hydration level, urine must be adjusted for dilution by creatinine correction, specific gravity correction, osmolality correction, or volume correction. In creatinine correction, urine concentrations are ratioed to creatinine concentrations (Middleton et al., 2016). Creatinine is a byproduct of protein catabolism, excreted in urine at a relatively constant rate within individuals. Osmolality correction accounts for osmometry, the ratio of dissolved particles per unit of water. Specific gravity correction adjusts for the ratio between the urine density and water density generally measured by refractometry, the ratio of light refraction in air versus the urine sample (Middleton et al., 2016; Wyness et al., 2016). Volume corrected methods normalise the sample concentrations to the urinary flow rate, the urine volumes excreted over time (Middleton et al., 2016). Exposure levels based on urine data are consequently expressed as the substance concentration in adjusted urine samples.

9.10 Appendix 4: Experimental design of the developmental toxicity study

The original experimental toxicity study was performed in 2005 and submitted as a key study for developmental toxicity in the REACH registry of BP-3. The study was performed in accordance with the guidelines for testing of chemicals as internationally agreed upon by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). The original testing method followed the OECD 414 Prenatal Developmental Toxicity study guideline and complied with conditions of Good Laboratory Practices (OECD, 2018). BP-3 was tested for prenatal developmental toxicity in time-mated female Wistar rats. Test animals were exposed to BP-3 in doses of 40, 200, and 1000 mg/kg bw/day orally administered by gavage feeding of the BP-3 doses suspended in a corn oil vehicle. Per dose, a group of 25 animals was tested, and dose-groups were compared to 25 control animals. The control animals were parallelly dosed with the corn oil vehicle. For each group of animals, a standard volume of 5 ml/kg bw/day corn oil was administered. Animals were exposed to doses or vehicle once every day for 14 consecutive days. Exposure started on day 6 post coitum and lasted

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through day 19 post coitum. On day 20 post coitum, the expected day of parturition, all females were terminally sacrificed, and the dams and their fetuses were macroscopically examined.